

Constraining Exoplanetary Physical and Orbital Parameters with TAR-Fit

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Abstract

Photodynamical modeling of star systems using available Kepler transit photometry and radial velocity observations has provided unique constraints on physical parameters of stars, providing insight into stellar structure and formation models (Carter et al. 2011). The inclusion of forthcoming astrometric measurements from the ongoing ESA Gaia mission will help improve the accuracy and precision of these models by constraining the orbital motion of stars around the system barycenter in the plane of the sky. Here I use the self-developed Transit, Astrometry, and RV Fitter (TAR-Fit) photodynamical model to update the parameters of the KOI-126 system, first reported in Carter et al. (2011). KOI-126 is a triply-eclipsing stellar system composed of a low-mass binary in orbit around a solar-type star. I use a Bulirsch-Stoer numerical integrator written in C to compute the dynamics of the system in a heliocentric frame, and run a Markov Chain Monte Carlo fitting process calculating the chi-square value for the simulated transits, astrometry, and RV data produced by the integrator compared to observational data. The best-fit model parameters I calculated for the dataset from Carter et al. (2011) were consistent with their parameters, but not consistent with the full photometric dataset, and required slight tweaks in the orbital angles of the system in order to fit all the transits. The evolution of the parameters for KOI-126 throughout the 7 years of Kepler and radial velocity observations provides strong constraints on the best-fit parameter values.

keywords: models – photodynamics; photometry – transits, Kepler, TESS; astrometry – Gaia; radial velocities

1. Introduction

Photodynamical modeling is the method by which physical parameters of stellar and planetary systems can be measured precisely through numerical integration in time of the Newtonian gravitational interactions between massive bodies (Carter et al. 2011, hereafter C11). By using available observational data, such as transit photometry and radial velocity measurements, the accuracy of these models can be ascertained. This process can be iterated many times while varying the free parameters to obtain a best-fit model for each system. The concept of photodynamical modeling can be traced back to the first discussion of transit timing variations (TTVs; Holman & Murray 2005, Agol et al. 2005). The interactions between different masses in the system can create measurable deviations from Keplerian orbits. For example, mutual interactions between two stars, two planets, or a star and a planet are significant and are proportional to the masses of the two objects. These effects can change multiple parameters of the system, including the inclination of the system to the observer's line of sight and the position of the planet in its orbit after one orbital period. This causes noticeable impacts to the observable transit signature by changing the impact parameter of the planet on the star in its transit, which affects the length and depth of the transit, as well as the time of the center of transit. These effects also stack up over time, change dramatically at orbital conjunctions, and can be periodic if the orbiting bodies are in resonance. By modeling these interactions using Newtonian gravitational mechanics, general/special relativistic effects, and/or tidal forces where necessary, the masses and other parameters of the interacting bodies can be calculated from the deviations in the transits.

1.1 Principles of photodynamical modeling

Transit observations, which have revolutionized the exoplanet field with the discoveries made by NASA's Kepler Space Telescope (Borucki et al. 2010, etc.), only provide estimations on a few parameters of the system, such as the radius ratio between the primary star and its planets or smaller stars and the inclination between each of the objects, which for transiting objects is known to be near 90 degrees for these edge-on orbits. However, by observing the interactions between multiple orbiting objects, many more parameters (such as the mass of each object) can be constrained, which is not possible in a single-orbiting or non-interacting system. Hence, photodynamical modeling is sometimes the only way to make measurements of such parameters with our current technology.

With photodynamical modeling, using a combination of data from different observational types along with the equations of motion that govern gravitational interactions, scientists have the ability to simulate the orbital mechanics of the system, and from that infer multiple important system parameters such as the mass and radius of each object. These values are particularly important for exoplanetary science because astronomers can then calculate a density for the planet, which then allows them to infer a composition and a formation history, as well as an idea about the atmospheric conditions.

Current versions of photodynamical models utilize transit photometry from Kepler, the Wide-Angle Search for Planets (WASP, Street et al. 2003), and other transit hunting missions, as well as radial velocity (RV) measurements from ground-based spectrographs at locations all around the world. Transit data provide constraints on the radius, inclination, and orbital angles of the system. The depth of the transit is proportional to the square of the radius ratio, $(R_p/R_*)^2$

(Seager & Mallén-Ornelas 2003, Winn 2010), but additional data are required to solve for the absolute stellar radius.

Precise stellar spectra can deliver the temperature, metallicity, and stellar spectral type. These spectra can then be combined with detailed stellar models, such as the PHOENIX library (Husser et al. 2013), and offer an accurate measurement of the stellar radius, from which the planetary radius can be calculated. For some stars, the spectra can also be combined with asteroseismology if a precise, long-term photometric time-series exists (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996). Asteroseismology can give unique insight to the mechanisms powering the star and provide a measurement of the star's density, which can then be joined with the spectra to calculate a mass for the star and from that, the stellar and planetary radii.

RV observations can obtain measurements of the entire orbit of the companion object, including the eccentricity and all of the orbital angles except for the inclination. RVs also give an estimate of the mass of the perturbing body from the ratio of the mass of the perturber to the mass of the central body. However, that measurement is degenerate with the inclination, which is unconstrained by RV data, so only a lower limit for the companion mass can be inferred (Struve 1952, etc.).

Either type of observation will give the period of the orbital companion, and if the mass of the primary star is known (such as through spectroscopic analysis), Kepler's Third Law can be used to calculate the semi-major axis of the orbit. Photodynamical models can generate precise, detailed dynamical positions using Newtonian gravitational mechanics and calculate simulated transit photometry and RVs to match the observations.

In addition, many second-order effects can be modeled to improve the accuracy of the simulation. Stellar limb darkening takes into account the varying brightness of the stellar disk

across its surface and models it as a function of the radius of the star, usually quadratic in nature (Mandel & Agol 2002). Finite-speed-of-light corrections have been known since Ole Roemer's studies of Io eclipsing Jupiter in 1675, where the slight changes in distance between the observer and the source affects the time of the eclipse because the speed of light is finite. Both of these corrections will be elaborated in Section 2.

1.2 Input data

The primary observational transit data that I use in my photodynamical modeling come from the Kepler Space Telescope, which during its primary mission from 2009-2014 observed ~100,000 stars in a 10° by 10° patch of sky between Cygnus and Lyra, looking for dips in the signal of these stars that were <100 parts per million (see e.g., Borucki et al 2010, Caldwell et al. 2010, Koch et al. 2010). Stars that show periodic fluctuations of this order of magnitude or greater were flagged by the Kepler team starting around Quarter 3 as objects of interest due to the potential for observing eclipses from planetary and/or multi-stellar systems (Jenkins et al. 2010).

RV observations come from multiple ground-based high-resolution spectrographs located all around the world. For KOI-126, the current RV data comes from the Tillinghast Reflector Echelle Spectrograph (TRES, Latham, Sasselov, and Szentgyorgyi 2006) at Fred Whipple Observatory in Arizona and the Robert G. Tull Coudé Spectrograph (Tull et al. 1995) on the 2.7-meter Harlan J. Smith Telescope at McDonald Observatory near Fort Davis, Texas. Other Northern Hemisphere spectrographs that perform RV follow up for planetary transit candidates include the High Accuracy Radial velocity Planetary Searcher – North (HARPS-N, Cosentino et al. 2012) at the Roque de los Muchachos Observatory on La Palma in the Canary Islands, and the

High Resolution Echelle Spectrograph (HIRES, Vogt et al. 1994) on Keck in Hawaii. In the Southern Hemisphere, HARPS (Mayor et al. 2003) at the ESO La Silla Observatory in Chile and the Cryogenic Infrared Echelle Spectrograph (CRIRES, Kaeufl et al. 2004) at the Very Large Telescope in Chile cover the southern sky. These spectrographs can provide tens of meter-level precision on radial velocity measurements and cover all latitudes.

1.3 Notable systems

KOI-126 is one such interesting object observed by Kepler where photodynamical modeling has been exploited in order to understand the properties of the system and uncover new insights about stellar populations. KOI-126 is a triply-eclipsing stellar system consisting of two low-mass stars in a ~ 1.77 -day period binary system that orbits a solar-type star with a ~ 34 day period (Carter et al 2011; hereafter C11). From the interesting shape of the stellar eclipses, previous studies have inferred a unique system geometry for KOI-126. The mutual inclinations of all of the orbits are nearly edge-on, because transits between all three stars have been observed (here I use “transits” interchangeably for planetary transits and stellar eclipses, as this model was built primarily to model exoplanet systems). These distinct multi-transits deliver a wealth of information about the masses, radii, and orbits of the three stars in the system. Some of the transits observed in the first five quarters by Kepler that are reported in C11 show mutual transits of the low-mass stars that comprise the outer binary while they cross in front of the larger primary star. This activity allows the model to determine the dynamics of the system very well and establish values with very small uncertainties for the masses, radii, and orbital parameters.

Photodynamical modeling is nominally used to investigate interesting planetary systems, an example of which is the two-planet system Kepler-36 (Carter et al. 2012). For this system,

Kepler not only had precise transit photometry but also asteroseismology. Kepler revealed oscillations of the primary star due to the excitation of sound waves by the turbulent stellar atmosphere, which allows for a measurement for the stellar density. This, combined with high-resolution spectra that provide the stellar metallicity and effective temperature, can be used to calculate precise values for the mass and radius of Kepler-36. From here, the photodynamical models used these values to simulate the system, and calculated a fit for a two-planet system in a near 6/7 orbital resonance with strong TTVs. The photodynamical simulations of the chaotic evolution of this system were still able to fit the observed data well, due to the constraints from the asteroseismology and the TTVs. The two planets in the system have orbital periods only ~2.5 days apart, yet their densities differ by nearly an order of magnitude, which is unique amongst known exoplanet systems. This system is in huge contrast to general formation theories for exoplanet systems, and provides strong evidence for planetary migration from inside vs. outside the host star's snow line.

Other than the two systems modeled by Carter et al. (2011, 2012), a few additional systems have also been simulated using photodynamical modeling to uncover new insights about the dynamics of the planetary systems. The circumbinary planet Kepler-16, which was the first confirmed transiting planet found orbiting a double-star system, was modeled with a three-body system of gravitational interactions that itself was a modified version of the same photodynamical code used in C11 (Doyle et al. 2011). With the unique TTV and TDV constraints provided by having multiple interacting bodies, they were able to determine absolute values with the lowest measured radius uncertainty at that time. Migaszewski, Słonina, and Goździewski (2012) performed direct N-body integration of the six-planet Kepler-11 system, which was discovered using TTVs (Lissauer et al. 2011). Using a similar model to Carter et al.

(2011, 2012), they were able to constrain the mass of the outermost planet, which was validated in the discovery paper but poorly characterized, to less than 30 Earth masses. They were also able to determine the range of the mutual inclinations between planet pairs (b, c) and (d, e), which were both within 5° .

Mills and Fabrycky (2016) also used photodynamical modeling with 3-body integration of the Newtonian equations of motion to characterize the dynamics of two Saturn-mass planets around a star with a wide binary companion in the Kepler-108 system. By assuming that Kepler-108B is the host and disregarding the effect of Kepler-108A, they found that the mutual inclination between the planets is high (15°), with the orbital periods and inclinations inconsistent with a disk migration origin. Along the same lines, Mills et al. (2016) used a similar version of photodynamical modeling to characterize the system parameters of the four-planet Kepler-223 system, where the previous observations had a signal-to-noise ratio too low to make precise measurements of the system architecture. They discovered a chain of sub-Neptune planets in a 3:4:6:8 resonance, which was the first such system ever modeled and provided the best test-bed so far to test the in-situ formation vs. migration hypotheses. They found that the system was too well constructed to have been formed in place, and must have migrated to that state. In another case, Mills and Fabrycky (2017) modeled the extremely compact system Kepler-444, which has five sub-Earth planets with orbital periods between 3 and 10 days. In particular, the two outermost planets, Kepler-444d and Kepler-444e, are close to an orbital resonance and have strong TTV and TDV features, which allows for detection confidence in the masses, around only 3.5% the mass of the Earth.

A slightly different version of photodynamical modeling was also used to determine the system architecture of one of the most interesting recent planetary systems to date, TRAPPIST-1,

the first planetary system found by the Transiting Planets and Planetesimals Small Telescope (TRAPPIST, Jehin et al. 2011). Three planets were described in the original discovery paper (Gillon et al. 2016). However, using precise photometric modeling and MCMC analysis, Gillon et al. (2017) was able to determine that the signal from the outermost original planet was a composite signal created from three different planets transiting the host star. In addition, they found two more planets orbiting the star, for an amazing total of 7 planets. Each of these planets is approximately Earth-sized or smaller, and they all orbit the star, an ultracool red dwarf star located about 12 parsecs away, in less than 20 days. Planets e, f, and g, which are the fourth through sixth planets from the star, also orbit in the habitable zone of the star, where water would be a liquid on the surface of the planet.

1.4 Astrometry

Astrometry is the precise measurement of the position and motion of stars in the plane of the sky. The movement of stars can come from multiple sources: the proper motion as they move through the galaxy relative to us, parallax due to the Earth's orbit around the Sun, and the "tugs" caused by orbital companions. The first two forms of stellar motion are much larger in magnitude ($10^2 - 10^5$) than the effect a planet would have on its host star, so they must be measured and subtracted out before the stellar wobble due to just a planet can be detected. The signal strength of all three effects is dependent on the distance between the stars and us. Nearby stars will have the most motion on the sky, but they will also be the most accurate targets to measure possible motion caused by orbiting planetary companions, due to the precision with which their proper motion and parallactic motion can be measured and removed from the observations.

Adding astrometry to current versions of photodynamical models will supplement them nicely, as astrometric measurements are applicable over a wider parameter space for values such as the orbital inclinations and semi-major axes. Astrometry can be used to confirm stellar and planetary values of systems previously discovered by transits and RV measurements, although the signal strength is dependent on the mass and semi-major axis of the orbit. On the other hand, astrometry is also sensitive to longer orbital periods than transits and RV, and the strength of the signal is less dependent on the inclination, which is one of the main limitations for the other two observation types. Transits need nearly edge-on orbits ($i \approx 90^\circ$) in order to be observed, and RVs. For astrometry a nearly face-on orbit ($i \approx 0^\circ$) would have a stronger signal, measuring two components of the motion in the plane of the sky, but an edge-on orbit would still provide a weaker signal containing only one component of that motion. This still breaks the degeneracy that orbital inclination has on RV mass measurements, and allows for non-transiting systems to be analyzed. For photodynamical modeling, astrometry will be possible with both face-on and edge-on orbits, so models that are able to include a combination of transit photometry, astrometry, and radial velocity measurements will be able to constrain the orbital motion on the plane of the sky as well as in and out of it, remove the mass-inclination degeneracy from the RV measurements, and calculate extremely precise orbital motions for exoplanets around their host stars.

Current astrometry has been defined by the Hipparcos mission (Perryman et al. 1997), which mapped the whole night sky over a period of 3.5 years and calculated the positions, parallactic motion, and annual proper motion of around 118,000 stars, or about 3 stars per square degree. The completeness level of these targets was 9th magnitude, with a limiting magnitude down to 12.4, and the limit to the precision was about 0.7-0.9 milliarcseconds. The values and

errors were slightly refined by van Leeuwen (2005), but have remained between 0.5 and 1 milliarcsecond for the past decade. An exciting new development in the past three years is the high-precision astrometry from the Gaia satellite, which released its first set of data in September 2016 (Brown et al. 2016). Throughout its mission, Gaia will observe 90% of the night sky and calculate the astrometric signature greater than 100 microarcseconds in the plane of the sky for stars brighter than 20th magnitude, with a precision limit around the order of 10 microarcseconds for stars brighter than 13th magnitude (Perryman et al. 2014). This is especially good for exoplanet host stars, as Gaia will be able to resolve the orbiting planets' small tugs to an unprecedented degree of accuracy.

1.5 Future applications

In the future, photodynamical modeling will have a wide range of available targets to analyze. In particular, the simulations will be able to make use of systems discovered by the K2 continuation to the original Kepler mission (Howell et al. 2014) and those observed by the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS, Ricker et al. 2014), which is scheduled to launch in December 2018. TESS will scan approximately 90% of the night sky throughout the first two years of its mission. Its goal is to find super-Earth exoplanets around the nearby bright stars, which will be ideal for future follow-up from ground-based RV observations (Sullivan et al. 2015). Furthermore, these bright targets will automatically have been observed by the Gaia mission, which covers the entire sky down to 20th magnitude, so precise astrometry can also be obtained. This combination will allow for precise measurement of parameters in the systems.

In this paper I determine constraints on the physical and orbital parameters of the triple-stellar system KOI-126 using a photodynamical model named TAR-Fit that combines

photometric transit flux measurements, spectroscopic radial velocity data, and currently-simulated precise astrometric observations. This paper is organized as follows. In section 2, I provide an overview of the photodynamical modeling code, written in C with a Python wrapping top-level program. Section 3 describes the sets of observations obtained from Kepler photometry, ground-based RV measurements, and simulated Gaia astrometry. I describe the Markov Chain Monte Carlo model fitting process written in Python that I employed to calculate the best-fit model in section 4, and in section 5 I state the analysis process and how I obtained the best fit model. In section 6 I detail how simulated astrometry can be created and used to test the astrometric capabilities of the model, and I show the results of the numerical integration and model fit on the parameters for the KOI-126 system in section 7. In section 8 I compare my results to those stated in C11 and discuss the key insights I have obtained, and in section 9 I state my conclusions about the KOI-126 system and possible further implementations of the photodynamical model.

2. Photodynamical Model

The photodynamical modeling program I am using to analyze KOI-126 is called the Transit, Astrometry, and Radial Velocity Fitting program (TAR-Fit). The majority of TAR-Fit is written in C in order to maximize computational speed, and it has the ability to run code that is written in Fortran. It can be linked to Python as well via the Python structure “ctypes” and be run simply as a function in a larger Python program. The generic structure of the main program starts with loading in an initial conditions file along with files for the three different types of observational data. The program then iterates the dynamics of the system over the entire dataset, generating model data points along the way. Finally, once a full model has been created, the code

calculates the chi-square value for the model as a test to see how favorable the initial conditions are. This can be hooked up to a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) or other iterated fitting process and be run thousands of times to find the most likely set of physical and orbital parameters for the system (see Figure 1 for a linear graphical representation of the overall structure of TAR-Fit).

2.1 Bulirsch-Stoer numerical integrator

The heart of the program is the Bulirsch-Stoer numerical integrator contained in a separate C file called by the main. The Bulirsch-Stoer algorithm uses rational functions for extrapolation along with the modified midpoint method to find numerical solutions to ordinary differential equations (ODEs) with high accuracy and relatively low computational requirements (Stoer and Bulirsch 1980). The modified midpoint method takes the Euler method of solving ODEs and modifies it by using many steps over the interval. Fitting the extrapolation down to a step size of 0 with rational functions instead of polynomial functions makes the algorithm more efficient. Also, due to the error series of the modified midpoint method having only even powers of the step size, adding more steps greatly increases the accuracy of the algorithm. For more on Bulirsch-Stoer integration and extrapolation using the modified midpoint method, see e.g., Gear (1971), Deuffhard (1983), Deuffhard (1985), Shampine & Baca (1983), and Hairer, Nørsett & Wanner (1993).

A benefit of using the modified midpoint method is that it is only a second-order model, meaning it only needs two derivatives in order to solve the differential equation. Thus, it is very applicable in situations where constant acceleration can be approximated, such as Newtonian gravitation. The Bulirsch-Stoer numerical integrator takes as input a set of physical bodies

Figure 1: Graphic detailing the process by which the photodynamical code will run, wrapped inside of a Python MCMC process. This MCMC process can also be done in another function in C to make the model all one program. Note that a “large” time step is still much shorter than the period of the inner binary, but is larger relative to the ~30 second “small” time step.

containing their masses, positions, and current velocities, defined as a phase state in the program. It then uses Newton’s laws of mechanics along with the inverse square law of gravitation to calculate the next step in the integration, for a set of arbitrary time steps. For precision only to the scale of hundreds of kilometers, which is small compared to the radii and orbital semi-major axes of the stars in the system, it is numerically efficient and accurate to model the mechanics of

KOI-126 in a Newtonian way, disregarding most effects of general relativity such as precession of the orbits and changes in eccentricity.

2.2 Coordinate frames

Currently, the program is only set to accept physical parameters in the Keplerian Jacobi coordinate system, because that was the coordinate system in which C11 ran their analysis on KOI-126. The Keplerian Jacobi coordinate system is a hierarchical coordinate system, in which the main body of the system and an orbiting companion (usually either the closest to the main body and/or the next most massive body) are modeled first. Then, a third body is added in, and its parameters are specified with respect to the center of mass of the first two bodies. If a fourth body exists, its parameters are entered with respect to the center of mass of the first three bodies, and this can be iterated outwards for the number of bodies in the system, constantly modeling the next object in the system with respect to the center of mass of all of the inner orbiting bodies.

All of the system parameters are specified via Keplerian orbital mechanics, so an orbit is completely constrained by its semi-major axis a , eccentricity e , inclination i , argument of periapse ω , mean anomaly M , and longitude of ascending node Ω . However, transit photometry cannot determine the longitude of ascending node of the binary center-of-mass with respect to the central star by itself, but it can be set to 0 degrees on input without loss of generality.

Astrometric measurements will be able to determine the longitude of ascending node, which is the angle relative to our view of horizontal of the orbital motion for the companions and the primary star. The longitude of ascending node of the low-mass binary for KOI-126 is then constrained relative to the artificially defined angle of the main orbit. In the case of KOI-126, for ease of calculation, C11 set the smaller low-mass binary star as the main orbiting body in the

Keplerian Jacobi frame, the larger low-mass star as the secondary orbiting body, and the primary star in the system as the third body with respect to the center of mass of the low-mass binary stars.

The numerical integration is run in the heliocentric frame, which is defined as the frame in which the massive central star is at the origin in three-dimensional space and does not move in time. In order to run the program with the original parameters read in from C11, this required multiple frame conversions to be written into the program, between Jacobi, heliocentric, and barycentric coordinates. The barycentric frame is located at the center of mass of the system, which for planetary systems is located near or within the radius of the star, but for multiple stellar systems can be anywhere between the different components in the system. In this frame, all elements of the system orbit the center of mass, and their positions and velocities undergo orbital oscillations in time as a result. It is in this frame that radial velocity and astrometric measurements can be made, as these two observations measure for the primary star the velocity along the line-of-sight and the two-dimensional position in the plane of the sky, respectively, which cannot be measured in the heliocentric frame.

The first conversion sends the initial Keplerian-Jacobi frame into the more conventional Cartesian-heliocentric coordinates, albeit with the frame still centered on the smaller of the two stars in the low-mass binary. These six arguments can be directly transposed into positions and velocities in three dimensions in a Cartesian frame. Then, this heliocentric frame is converted into the barycentric frame, the center of which is located much closer to the single solar-type star, because it is six times more massive than each of the other two stars. The indices of the different stars inside the phase state are then swapped, so that the most massive star holds the first position in the array that comprises the phase state. Finally, the barycentric frame is then

switched back into a heliocentric frame, but one that is now centered on the most massive star, so that the phase state is now ready for integration in the heliocentric frame required to observe the transit photometry from Kepler.

2.3 Initialization and integration

At initialization of a fitting run, the user will send in an initial parameters file, containing all the physical parameters of the system. These parameters have been read into an alternative system of measurements, where the units of length are measured in AU, units of mass are measured in solar masses, and the units of time are measured in days. This causes interesting values for the universal constants of the speed of light, $c = 173 \text{ AU/day}$, as well as the Newtonian gravitational constant, $G = 2989 \text{ AU}^3 \text{ day}^{-2} M_{\odot}^{-1}$. All output from the program is also specified in this alternative measurement system, so values for the radial velocity and astrometry models are converted into kilometers per second and milliarcseconds, respectively, at the end of the program. For Keplerian-Jacobi coordinates, only the masses and semi-major axes are reported with these values, while the radii are initialized in solar radii and are converted to AU inside the program.

The integrator starts at the user-specified initial time, denoted T_0 , and begins to integrate with relatively large time steps (~ 1 hour). Another file sent in by the user contains the observation times, durations, and types in chronological order, which is then checked after every step of the integration to see if the program has entered an exposure. If so, it denotes the type of exposure and jumps the phase state back to the start of the exposure, before taking much smaller time steps dependent on the minimum length of all the exposures (< 55 seconds due to the short cadence Kepler data). The integrator then calls the correct model observation calculation for the

current exposure type, and a data point at each small time step is simulated. At the end of the exposure, the set of different data points calculated via integration inside the exposure are averaged together to create one model data point for that specific exposure, which is then saved for the chi-square fitting process.

2.4 Transit photometry calculations

For the photodynamical model, a majority of the data come from transit photometry, since the <1 minute cadence of the short-cadence Kepler data allows for orders of magnitude more observations than the ~ 30 minute RV observations and >1 hour variable-cadence astrometry from Gaia. Accordingly, most of the simulated data points are photometric, and contribute to most of the chi-square fitting. Thus, the photometry calculation function must be as accurate as possible. To simulate the photometry value, the method loops over all the smaller, transiting bodies to check if its position within the x-y plane is within the radius of the primary star and if its z position is in the desired direction. Traditionally, to preserve a right-handed coordinate system, +z is defined as towards the observer and in front of the primary star, whereas -z is defined away from the observer and behind the primary star. If these conditions are not met, then the value of the photometry is set to 1 and the integration continues on to the next small step in the exposure.

If the conditions are met, then the program runs a Fortran function called “occultquad” (Mandel & Agol 2002; Eastman, Gaudi, & Agol 2013), which computes the depth of the transit at the specific x-y position of the transiting bodies. In particular, the function determines the radius ratio of the transiting object to the light-emitting object, in order to calculate the amount of the surface of the primary star is occulted by the transiting body. By including the

measurement of the precise position of the transiting object, the amount of light blocked by the transiting object is calculated normally using a quadratic limb-darkening function. Limb-darkening is non-uniformities in the brightness of the primary star as a function of its radius. Most models of limb-darkening conclude that it is radially symmetric (i.e. the same for each angle at a given radius), and that the light drops off as a function of two parameters via the following equation

$$I(r) = I(0)(1 - u_1(1 - \sqrt{1 - r^2}) - u_2(1 - \sqrt{1 - r^2})^2) \quad (1)$$

These limb-darkening parameters vary from star to star, and thus are set as free parameters in the model and allowed to fluctuate until the model's chi-square value is minimized. For the primary star in KOI-126, C11 reported $u_1 = 0.39 \pm 0.03$ and $u_2 = 0.22 \pm 0.04$.

The C program also counts the number of transits and the number of transiting objects in the system in order to check for overlapping transits. If there are multiple transits of the main body at the same time, the program then looks at the precise position and radius of each of the objects and determines if two (or more) of the objects overlap. If there is some geometric overlap of the transiting bodies, the program calculates the ratio of the overlap area to the area of the larger transiting object contributing to the overlap and reduces the depth of the transit by that ratio. This is applicable only when the transiting bodies are considered dark, i.e. that no flux is being contributed to the system by these objects. For light-emitting transiting objects, we can instead determine which of the bodies is blocking light from the other, determine the percentage of the light from the middle object that is being occulted, and remove that amount of light from the system flux.

2.5 Radial velocity calculations

For the RV calculations, the program first gets the heliocentric velocity of each transiting body and calculates the barycentric velocities of the bodies from these values inside the heliocentric-barycentric coordinate frame conversion. Then, using the mass-velocity relation to calculate the effect of the transiting objects on the primary star, and then cumulatively adds together the radial velocity of the primary star due to each of the other bodies. This value is then checked with the velocity calculated using the barycentric frame. This gives a simulated data point at the specific time step in the integration, similar to the photometric observations, which is then averaged together with all of the data points inside an RV exposure to give one exposure-averaged RV calculation. For a ~30 minute exposure that is typical for RV measurements and the small time step defined by the photometric observations, there are many more time steps averaged together into one RV measurement than for one transit data point, which for small orbits may mean a loss of data since the speed of the main body might differ at the beginning and end of the exposure. However, the velocities for KOI-126 do not change much during the exposure, as the length of exposure is about 6.1×10^{-4} of the value of the period of the low-mass binary around the primary star, so the exposure-averaged value does not suffer from this effect.

2.6 Astrometric calculations

For the astrometry calculations, the heliocentric phase state is converted back into the barycentric frame, and the position of the primary star in the x-y plane (in the plane of the sky) is recorded for each integration point in the exposure. The exposure average is calculated in the same way as the transit photometry and the RV observations, leaving one simulated data point per exposure. The distance of the star from the barycenter is calculated in AU, and then is

converted into arcseconds using the distance to the system, which for KOI-126 I set to 600 pc. There is currently no distance measurement for the system from Hipparcos or Gaia, but if a system is observed by Hipparcos or Gaia, we will then have accurate distance measurements for the system using its parallax, which is an effect created by the movement of the Earth around the Sun, and trigonometry. This effect can either be removed prior to the data being inserted into the program, or it can also be modeled with the astrometry, allowing the distance to the system to be a free parameter and constrained by the photodynamical model.

2.7 Chi-square calculations

Finally, after the end of the integration, the program calculates a chi-square fit for the model. The chi-squared value is found by summing the squares of the differences between the data and the model, and then dividing by the error, as shown in the following formula

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(x_d^2 - x_m^2)}{\sigma_x} \quad (2)$$

This value was summed up for all the exposures of each observational type for each data point in the integration. At the end of the loop, the program returns the total chi-square value. The model is considered the best-fit when the chi-squared value is minimized, as the difference between the data and the model is the smallest. This chi-squared value is calculated for every run of the main method of the photodynamical model. As the parameters are modified, as seen in Figure 10, the chi-squared value changes to reflect the new model's fit to the data. For large data sets, a better understanding of the fit can be found in the reduced chi-squared value, the chi-squared value divided by the degrees of freedom in the distribution, which is one less than the number of total observations, minus the number of degrees of freedom in the fitted model. A reduced chi-squared

value near 1 is considered a good fit, as the difference between the model and the data is proportional to the observational error and can thus be attributed to it.

2.8 New developments

The code for the photodynamical model was mostly finished at the start of the project, but development was necessary in order to optimize the functionality of the code. Originally, the program was accessing the disk memory at multiple points throughout the program, in order to write output files. I established a “debug” parameter initialized to False that suppresses all the disk access except for reading the initial conditions file and the input data files. When “debug” is switched to true, the file access and output processes are reinstated. Also, the number of time steps per exposure was set at an arbitrary value, and I refined it to be close to the Kepler short-cadence exposure time, so that fewer calculations were being performed per exposure by an order of magnitude.

In addition, I optimized the initial time of the program integration to the beginning of the first exposure, and aligned all the different observations in chronological order, including interspersing the RV and astrometry observations, when applicable, with the transit photometry. This allows the integration to constantly move forward, instead of having to backtrack at the end of the photometry to the initial state of the first RV or astrometry exposure. Finally, for each exposure I checked to see which type of observation was occurring, and only calculated the simulated model point for that data type, instead of calculating every data point for each type. This reduced the runtime for one iteration of the program only using the first transit from the one-second level down to ~60 milliseconds, allowing for an iterative process like MCMC to only require about an hour to run 100,000 steps to find the best-fit parameters for the first transit.

2.9 Light travel time

Another form of optimization included correcting for the finite speed of light, adjusting the time of observations. The system is moving in all three dimensions on the sky, with the movement into and out of the plane of the sky measured using the RV offset calculated by TRES and McDonald observations. However, the effect of the proper motion is orders of magnitude smaller than the amount of time the light has to travel the full distance from the star, and is also stretched out over a much larger time period, so is essentially negligible for the ~ 1 -minute intervals at which the photometry observations were recorded. For the analysis performed in C11, they removed the barycentric radial velocity drift over time, because it only changes by a few minutes over the 8 transits they analyzed. Also, it only affected the measurement of the orbital periods by significant amounts, but the rest of the parameters were not changed by greater than 0.1σ . However, for the full dataset that comprises of more than 4 times as much data, this drift in the light travel time will be more significant and therefore should be included in the model.

The more noticeable effect that comes from the finite speed of light is in the orbital motion of the system. As the three bodies orbit each other, the distance from us to the primary star changes by about 0.12 AU along the axis of our line of sight (see Figure 8 in Section 3.3), which corresponds to differences in the time on the order of a minute for the observed photons coming from the system. This effect is largest when the three stars are aligned perpendicular to us, as this is when the primary star is moving fastest away from us. When the primary star is in opposition, and the low-mass binary is transiting in front of it, it is not moving much in the z -direction, but measuring and correcting for this small amount in the light travel time still helps the model find the best fit.

In order to calculate this effect in the photodynamical model, I needed to use a root-finding algorithm to solve for the primary star’s distance from the barycenter and the retarded time at which the photons were emitted from the star at that distance. I solved the roots of the following equation for each data point,

$$d(t_r) - c(T - t_r) - \gamma(T - T_0) = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $d(t_r)$ is the star’s distance from the barycenter, T is the clock time at which an observer records the photon, t_r is the emitted time of the photon, γ is the motion of the barycenter of the system along the line of sight, and T_0 is the initial observation time as defined in Section 2.3. The root-finding algorithm returned a time and distance consistent with the primary star being near its farthest point away from us, as expected during a transit event for the low-mass binary. This decreased the chi-square value by 15% as compared to when light travel time correction is ignored.

3. Datasets

3.1 Transits

Transit photometry comes from the Kepler Space Telescope’s primary observing mission, which lasted from its launch in January 2009 until the second failure of a reaction wheel in 2014, which prevented stable pointing towards the original Kepler field. Altogether, the Kepler mission spans 17 quarters of data, all of it publicly available at the Barbara A. Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes (MAST), which is run by the Space Telescope Science Institute (STScI). Kepler had two observing modes, which are based on the length of the exposure: the long-cadence data has an exposure time of 29.6 minutes (1765 seconds), while the short-cadence data has exposure times that are only 54.18 seconds long. Coverage of the system for the entire 4

years of the Kepler mission would be comprised of over 60,000 data points for long-cadence photometry and over 2 million data points for the short-cadence data.

3.1.1 Long-cadence data

The long-cadence data from Kepler on KOI-126 lasts from Quarter 0 in the pre-mission stage through Quarter 17 at the end of the mission. I began my analysis by following the process stated in C11, starting with the Simple Aperture Photometry for Quarters 0-5 that can be downloaded from MAST (abbreviated “SAP_FLUX” in the data header). This was essentially the only data available for C11 at the time, as the corrections to the flux would not yet have been calculated. The SAP_FLUX is simply the raw flux from the star, which can vary slightly with factors such as stellar activity, instrumental effects like pixel response and detector biases, along with dips from transiting companions.

I first normalized the flux to a baseline of 1 by dividing by the median of the flux for that quarter. This step is shown in Figure 2 with a similar plot from C11 for comparison. To find each transit, I searched in a ~2 day window centered on each transit time mentioned in C11, and ensured that there was a noticeable drop in flux during that window. Then, I set the out-of-transit baseline flux as the area not within 2 hours of the beginning and end of the transit, so that I would not accidentally include part of the transit in the baseline flux calculations. Finally, I fit a second-order polynomial to the out-of-transit baseline flux in that 2 day window around each transit, and subtracted the fitted polynomial from the photometry to remove any long-term trends from the data.

This process worked well for each set of data in Quarters 0-5 except for Quarter 4, which still showed a strong linear trend at the beginning. I also discovered similar offsets in Quarters 8

Figure 2: Comparison of normalized flux (not baseline subtracted) from C11 (left) and my own data reduction pipeline (right). The similarity between the plots shows that my normalization method works.

and 9 when I analyzed the full 17 quarters of available Kepler long-cadence data. Instead of attempting to fit another linear polynomial to these specific quarters, I decided to deviate from the analysis in C11 and instead use the Pre-search Data Conditioning Simple Aperture Photometry (“PDCSAP_FLUX”), which was not available at the time that C11 performed its analysis but was added on as a Kepler photometry feature later on. To create the PDCSAP_FLUX, a simple polynomial fit is calculated for the baseline of each quarter of data, and then it is removed from that dataset. After taking each quarter and dividing by its new median, the resulting dataset is almost completely normalized, as there is only a small fluctuation around the central normalized value (see Figure 3), which can be cleaned out by hand if necessary.

3.1.2 Short-cadence data

KOI-126 was observed with short-cadence data starting in Quarter 3, once it was flagged by the Kepler team as an interesting transit candidate. For the short-cadence observations, each quarter is provided in three different data files, with each having its own distinct baseline value. I started with the raw SAP_FLUX again for all of Quarters 3-17, but some of the datasets in Quarters 8 and 9 do not exist in the MAST archive due to issues collecting data at this time, and the linear trends in Quarter 4 still remained. Using the PDCSAP_FLUX instead of the SAP_FLUX removed those trends again, just like for the long-cadence data. However, due to the large number of data points out of transit events, I decided to stitch together 1.5-day windows of data containing each transit, which drastically reduced the amount of runtime required for the model.

One transit event happened to occur during the transition between Quarters 12 and 13, so it was removed completely from the analysis, and I still was not able to gather data from Quarters 8 and 9, which left me with a total of 34 transit events spread over Quarters 3-17. Quarters 3-5, which were the short-cadence data that were analyzed in C11, show a total of 8 separate transit events of the stars in the low-mass binary passing in front of the larger star, with each event showing a distinct impact parameter and set of inner binary orbital parameters. These transits are shown in Figures 4 and 5. After collecting short-cadence data from the second transit in Quarter 3, I noticed that the background out-of-transit flux had a mean value slightly larger than 1, so I went back and calculated a linear fit to the baseline data and divided it out of the data.

Figure 3: Long-cadence data from Kepler, Quarters 0-5. (Top left) Raw SAP_FLUX, with an unusually large linear trend seen in the low-counts Quarter 4. (Top right) Normalized and baseline-subtracted SAP_FLUX, with the linear effect now dominating the light curve of Quarter 4. (Bottom left) PDCSAP_FLUX with baseline correction only. (Bottom right) Normalized and baseline-corrected PDCSAP_FLUX. Processing the SAP_FLUX raw data left behind the linear trends that can be seen between days 350 and 450 in the upper right panel, whereas taking the already baseline-corrected PDCSAP_FLUX and normalizing it provides a much better out-of-transit baseline for that time period, as seen in the bottom right panel. Further baseline subtraction is done on transit windows to remove any similar effects.

Transit 1

Transit 2

Transit 3

Transit 4

Figure 4: The first 4 transits analyzed by C11 in Quarters 3-5 as seen by Kepler short-cadence data. Transits 1, 2, and 4 are separate, sequential transits of the low-mass binary stars, whereas transit 3 shows a mutual transit where both stars in the low-mass binary are transiting the primary star at the same time. The stark contrast in the transit depths and durations between successive transit events are due to variations in the orbit of the low-mass binary. This affects the position and the speed at which the smaller stars move in front of the primary star, causing changes in the depths and durations of the transit events.

Transit 5

Transit 6

Transit 7

Transit 8

Figure 5: The second set of 4 transits in Quarters 3-5 as seen in short-cadence data. Transit 7 is a separate, sequential transit, while transits 5, 6, and 8 are all mutual transit events. In transits 5 and 6 the two smaller stars end up geometrically overlapping, which shows up as unusual ingress/egress features in the photometry and provide strong constraints on the physical parameters of the system. These precise data points will provide strict constraints on the positions and velocities of the stars in the system, which will increase the diagnostic power of the photodynamical model simulations of the system.

Then, I ran a 5σ cleaning to strip outliers that were more than 5 times the average of the 50 data points surrounding that specific point. I also ran a stricter 4σ cleaning process on the Quarter 4 early baseline, since some effects from the linear trend persisted past the first data cleaning I ran on it. This removed only a couple hundred data points over all, and some data points still looked to be strong outliers. However, most of the data were free of artifacts and systematic trends.

3.2 Radial Velocity

The 16 radial velocity measurements used in C11 come from two different high-resolution spectrographs across a period of 430 days in 2009 and 2010. Ten observations came from the TRES on the 1.5-meter Tillinghast Reflector Telescope at the Fred L. Whipple Observatory on Mount Hopkins, Arizona. TRES was commissioned in 2006 for ground-based radial velocity follow-ups of the Kepler planet candidates, and saw first light in 2009, same as Kepler. The medium fiber on TRES was used for these observations, and it has resolving power $R = 44000$ and a wavelength range of 385-910 nanometers. The other six were collected using the Tull Coudé Spectrograph at McDonald Observatory. The original Tull Coudé Spectrograph was set up in the 1970s, but it was updated in 1995 to a resolution $R = 60000$ over wavelength range 375-1000 nanometers.

These spectrographs observe elemental and molecular absorption lines along multiple spectral orders for the stellar spectrum of the primary star, measure the Doppler frequency shift of the lines due to the orbital motion of the object, and convert the measurement of the frequency shift into the velocity of the star into and out of the plane of the sky. The low-mass binary stars do not produce enough light to be measurable, about four orders of magnitude less than the

primary star. Using this, the orbital velocity of KOI-126 A was calculated from data taken from 2010 in C11 and a function was fit to the data that corresponded to a noticeably eccentric orbit for the low-mass stars in the outer binary. Since then, TRES has observed KOI-126 a total of ten more times, with four observations each in 2014 and six in 2016 that have much more precision than the early observations in 2009 and 2010. In addition, the earlier data points were cleaned, three more points were added in 2010, and the precision was increased. The model fit in C11, along with the full RV dataset, is plotted in Figure 6.

3.2.1 TRES Observations

In order to calculate the radial velocity of the target, the raw data that TRES observes needs to be cleaned. The first pass of the data is a manual check to remove any cosmic rays, which show up as strong, localized emission features that usually dominate the emission level of the rest of the spectra. The spectrum then goes through the continuum normalization process, where the flux of a flat field lamp is divided through so as to remove the blaze function of the spectrograph, and then the spectrum is normalized by a spline fit. After a measurement for the velocity is obtained, it gets adjusted by the zero point velocity of the spectrograph, which has fluctuated as a function of time throughout the seven years of TRES operation. Finally, the radial velocity of the system is given.

During the first few years, the stability of the zero point was very low, with deviations up to 400 m/s. After a fine-tuning adjustment in 2011, the zero point oscillations dropped to ~10 m/s, providing a much more stable baseline to calculate the radial velocity of the system for the observations from 2009 and 2010. In addition, the precision of the instrument was also weak in early runs from the instrument, as measured by RV standard stars. The original uncertainties and

Figure 6: (Top): Fit from C11 showing the absolute radial velocity of the primary star along with the residuals from the fit. (Bottom) Newest RV data, including thirteen additional measurements from TRES and more accurate values for older TRES observations.

scatter from the instrument in the measurements of KOI-126 were approaching 100 m/s. However, now the instrument precision is typically down to 10 m/s.

TRES has two different analysis types available for its data. For a relatively quick and accurate measurement, the TRES team can specify single-order calculations, where the analysis program picks one spectral order around the Mg I b triplet between 513.5 and 523.5 nanometers with which to calculate the velocity. In order to actually measure the radial velocity of the system, TRES then calculates the cross-correlation function between the cleaned data and a set of synthetic spectra in a library. The frequency shift at which the cross-correlation peak is highest corresponds to a radial velocity measurement for the system. For a more detailed and precise measurement, TRES also can do multi-order calculations, where the strongest observed spectrum is used as the template for the CCF.

The first set of TRES observations occurred across late 2010-early 2011, after Kepler flagged the system as “interesting” due to the transit shapes. From this set, there were a total of 10 observations that were used for analysis in C11. Since then, TRES continued observing KOI-126 in 2011, and went back two more times in late 2014 and late 2016. The observations from 2011 added an additional 2 radial velocity measurements, and the 2014 and 2016 datasets contained 4 and 6 exposures in each set, respectively, which brings the total number of TRES radial velocity points that I use in my analysis up to 23, spanning a long baseline from 2009 to 2016.

3.2.2 McDonald Observations

In addition to the TRES data, I also obtained the data from 6 observations of KOI-126 using the Robert G. Tull Coudé Spectrograph on the 2.7-meter Harlan J. Smith Telescope at

McDonald Observatory in west Texas. The radial velocity data points from the Tull Coudé Spectrograph were all taken between 2009 and 2010, corresponding to when this system was first discovered in the Kepler data. Even though the Tull Coudé spectrograph has higher resolution than TRES, it has higher error bars on the radial velocity measurement than TRES, and there is a systematic offset between the zero point in the McDonald and TRES observations which can be set as a free parameter that must be constrained in the model. However, these observations do complement the TRES data points by giving a comparison in the early 2010 data from TRES, where the spectrograph's zero point was still undergoing large fluctuations. Also, the McDonald observations provide earlier data to extend the overall coverage time of the system, which allows for more analysis to determine how the system dynamics are changing over longer periods of time.

3.3 Astrometry

Currently, there are no astrometric observations of KOI-126 accurate enough to detect the wobble of the primary star through its parallactic motion and proper motion on the sky, because it is fainter than the limits for the Hipparcos satellite. However, with the recent release of data from the Gaia satellite, high-precision astrometry will be available for many stars all over the night sky, and most likely including KOI-126. In order to predict whether or not Gaia could resolve the wobble of KOI-126 A due to the orbits of B & C, I can use Equation 6 from Perryman et al. (2014),

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{M_p}{M_*}\right) \left(\frac{a_p}{1AU}\right) \left(\frac{d}{1pc}\right)^{-1} \text{ arcsec} \quad (4)$$

where M_p is the mass of the binary KOI-126 (B, C), M_* is the mass of KOI-126 A, a_p is the semi-major axis of the orbit of KOI-126 (B, C) around KOI-126 A, and d is the distance to the system.

One complicating factor is that the distance to the star is unknown, since its parallax has not been measured. However, with precise spectroscopic measurements from C11 giving the effective temperature, metallicity, and rotational velocity of the primary star in the system, the distance can be modeled using a fit to the Dartmouth Stellar Evolution Database isochrones (Dotter et al. 2008). This fit provides a model distance of 600 pc to the system.

From the models predicted in C11, and using a model distance of 600 pc to the system, I predict that KOI-126 would have an astrometric signal of 100 microarcseconds (see Figure 7), which for its 13th magnitude primary star (SIMBAD) would be inside the limits of the satellite. The noise limits for Gaia come from the centroid limits for the 9 CCDs, which are added to the noise calculation as the average from each CCD, the attitude errors from both random and systematic modeling, and the calibration errors from the satellite, with the latter two considered constant throughout the field crossing (Perryman et al. 2014).

The simulated astrometry that the photodynamical model creates could be compared with observations from the Gaia satellite, if and when they are taken, to check the goodness of fit for the model and, if necessary, constrain the parameters even further. The simulated astrometry from the model can also have Gaussian noise added to it at the noise limit for Gaia data and fed back in as “real” astrometric data, which can then be analyzed by an MCMC process in addition to the photometry and RV data.

Figure 7: A diagram showing how the astrometric signal would be calculated, with $\alpha = \tan^{-1} \frac{r}{d}$.

For KOI-126, I set $d = 600$ pc, as we have no accurate measurement for the distance to the system, but we do have spectroscopic parameters for the primary star in the system that can be fit to stellar isochrones from the Dartmouth stellar evolution database to provide a distance estimation. The motion of the orbit of KOI-126 A, denoted as r in the above diagram, is approximately 0.06 AU. This disparity in the magnitudes of the distances allows for the use of the small-angle approximation, so we can set $\alpha = \frac{r}{d}$, which gives the magnitude of the angular motion of the system to be around 100 microarcseconds. This system would be able to be viewed by Gaia. Note that this diagram assumes that the proper motion and parallactic motion of the primary star both have been removed, and all the observer is seeing is motion due to the orbital companions. Also note that the motion of the primary star will be elliptical and not circular as is shown.

Figure 8: (Top) Positions of all three stars in the KOI-126 system in the X-Z plane over a period of 30 days, where the red and the green points are the low-mass binary stars and the blue is the primary star. This is measured in both AU (left and bottom) and in microarcseconds (right and top) (note the different axis scales), where the microarcseconds measurement assumes a distance of 600 pc. The observer is located parallel to the plane, so this is not what we would see from Earth. (Bottom): Close-up of the primary star.

Figure 9: (Top) Simulated astrometric measurements of all three stars in the X-Y plane over a period of 30 days, where the red and green points are the low-mass binary stars and the blue is the primary star. This is measured in both AU (left and bottom) and microarcseconds (right and top) (note the different axis scales), where the microarcseconds measurement is made assuming a system distance of 600 pc. The observer is looking down the z-axis, so this is what we would see from Earth. (Bottom) A close-up view of the primary star.

One key point to note is that astrometry measures the position of the photocenter of the system, not necessarily the barycenter. For objects too small to fuse hydrogen into helium, such as planets, the contrast in the optical can be around 10^{-7} , which would not be detectable by Gaia and thus the photocenter would be the center of the primary star. For stars undergoing fusion and producing their own light, the contrast can be many orders of magnitude larger, and thus the photocenter and the barycenter could be two different positions. However, in the case of KOI-126, the stars in the low-mass binary are small enough and the primary star large enough that the contrast in flux between them and the primary star is 10^{-4} , which is small enough to be disregarded at Gaia's sensitivity level.

4. MCMC Fitting

To find the best fit model, I use an iterative process known as a Markov Chain Monte Carlo process. A Markov chain, popularized by Andrei Markov in the early 20th century, is a stochastic model of a sequence of events where the probabilities of each event are only dependent on the state of the previous event (Hayes 2013). The Markov Chain Monte Carlo process, or MCMC, is an algorithm that takes samples from the probability distribution with the intent of forming a Markov Chain with the steady-state being the expected distribution of parameters. The most common forms of MCMC methods are the Random Walk Monte Carlo methods, of which the most popular is the Metropolis-Hastings method.

The Metropolis-Hastings algorithm is first described by Nicholas Metropolis and coauthors in 1953 and expanded and generalized by W.K. Hastings in 1970. The Metropolis-

Figure 10: First attempt at modifying parameters, shifting the mean anomaly and the inclination of the low mass binary with respect to the central star, as well as the inclination within the low mass binary. (Left): Data and shifted model with mean anomaly = 67.87, 66.87, 65.87, 64.87 degrees, in descending order with mutual inclination = 70.1 degrees and outer inclination = 92.1 degrees. (Center): Data and shifted model with mutual inclination = 70.1, 71.1, 72.1, 73.1 degrees, in descending order with mean anomaly = 66.87 degrees and outer inclination = 92.1 degrees. (Right): Data and shifted model with outer inclination = 92.1, 91.1, 90.1, 89.1 degrees, in descending order with mean anomaly = 66.87 degrees and mutual inclination = 70.1 degrees. Shifting the mean anomaly served to move when the system transits, and even decided if one of the low-mass stars transits. Adjusting the inner inclination did not seem to have much of an effect at this level. Changing the mutual inclination affected the depth and number of the low-mass transits. The chi-squared values of the different models in the left and right panels changed drastically, as the altered shapes of the new transit models increased the difference between the data and the models.

Figure 11: Same as Figure 10, but with the mutual transit event in the fifth transit. (Left): Data (mean anomaly 20.09 degrees) and shifted model with mean anomaly = 22.09, 21.09, 19.09, 18.09 degrees, in descending order with mutual inclination = 96.97 degrees and outer inclination = 92.1 degrees. (Center): Data (mutual inclination 96.97 degrees) and shifted model with mutual inclination = 98.97, 97.97, 95.97, 94.97 degrees, in descending order with mean anomaly = 20.09 degrees and mutual inclination = 92.1 degrees. (Right): Data (outer inclination 92.1 degrees) and shifted model with outer inclination = 94.1, 93.1, 91.1, 90.1 degrees, in descending order with mean anomaly = 20.09 degrees and mutual inclination = 92.1 degrees. Shifting the mean anomaly served to move when the system transits, and whether events occur at the same time. Adjusting the mutual inclination did not seem to have much of an effect at this level. Changing the outer inclination affected the depth and number of the low-mass transits. The chi-squared values of the different models in the left and right panels changed drastically, as the altered shapes of the new transit models increased the difference between the data and the models by 2 orders of magnitude.

Hastings algorithm generates a random walk step from an initial set of parameters in the N-dimensional parameter space, calculates the probability density, and accepts the walk automatically if the move provides a better probability than the previous step. If the move provides a worse probability, the algorithm creates a random number between 0 and 1 and tests the proposed probability density against the random number. If the random number is less than the probability, the move is accepted. If not, the move is denied, and another step on the random walk is generated using the previous initial set.

Using an MCMC approach provides quick sampling of parameter distributions, and it works well due to the relatively low probability of moving out of high-density regions in the probability distribution function. In particular, MCMC is a good algorithm for high-dimensional parameter spaces because its rejection probability does not increase exponentially with the number of dimensions in the space, a problem known as the “curse of dimensionality” (e.g. Bellman 1957, Bellman 1963), which many simple rejection sampling methods suffer. However, the MCMC process is not without its drawbacks. Samples drawn from the MCMC are correlated, and while the long-term trend is to correctly follow the probability distribution function, small subsets of the samples will be correlated due to being drawn from a similar local region in the parameter space. This causes the number of steps needed for an MCMC process to converge to increase

Also, marginalizing over two highly correlated variables can, in some instances, lead to a spot in parameter space with low probability density. This can happen specifically if the 2D density plot for the two parameters is banana shaped, so the average of one dimension gives the value at the bottom of the banana shape, but the average of the other dimension gives a point in the space above the banana. Finally, if the starting position is in a region of low-density in the

parameter space, it will cause the initial sampling to follow a different distribution of parameters, which would influence the final probability distribution. Therefore, a burn-in phase is often used, where the first hundred or thousand steps along the MCMC are discarded, so as to have a more accurate final distribution.

4.1 C single-variable approach

The first way I started out testing MCMC was by modifying a single-variable MCMC program written in C that was generously provided by my advisers. The program calls a function that produces a random step in one dimension of the parameter space. This parameter space is defined by the user, and can contain any positive integer number of parameters. The function generates a random integer between 1 and the length of the array, and randomly changes the parameter in the index of that random integer, based on a step-size delta value set up by the user. Once the new value has been introduced to the parameter set, the program tests to see whether the step in the parameter space is physically possible (i.e. that the values are non-negative, eccentricity is between 0 and 1, angles are between 0 and 360 degrees, etc.), as well as within user-initialized limits for the parameters. If it passes this step in the program, the function then runs the main integrator, which produces the chi-square value at the end of that test and runs the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm to decide whether or not to accept the jump in the parameter space.

This process is extremely fast for each sample in the MCMC, and it was written in C to optimize functionality. However, changing only one parameter at a time forces more steps to be necessary, as it could randomly attempt to alter the same parameter multiple times and be met with limited success. One way this could be further optimized is to implement a variation on a

multiple-try Metropolis-Hastings algorithm, where a large number of steps are all performed from an initial set of parameters, and the parameter step with the best chi-square value is found from that subset of samples and taken as the initial parameters for the next round of steps.

Another way to enhance the model is to restrict which parameters the model can change, or only allow it to change parameters which have not been changed recently. This setup takes away some of the randomness from the selection of the parameter to change, instead focusing on making sure all parameters eventually get altered or changing only parameters that should be changed in the model.

I encoded this MCMC process into the file containing the photodynamical model itself, adding it to the end of the program in C. This facilitated changes in the way that the main part of the code ran, including renaming and recasting the old “main” program to just return the chi-square value, as well as adding in the use of a “best parameters” file for easy storage and use of parameters for the MCMC. I also added three parameters to determine the length of the MCMC chain, how often to print out chi-square values, and the pseudo-random number generator seed, so that the values that come out between separate runs of the MCMC are consistent. This allows for multiple short runs while making small changes to the parameters to test the reactivity of the model to these parameters. After full optimization, the program was taking 4 seconds per 100 runs of 4000 data points, or processing about 100,000 data points per second. For the 17350 photometric data points analyzed in C11 and using 100,000 runs, this would take nearly 5 hours, and for 100,000 runs of the full dataset at ~75000 data points, this would take around 20 hours, so I either needed a dedicated computer that could run this nonstop for as long as is necessary, or figure out a way to make the program have multiple processes running at the same time (see Section 4.2).

The C process originally was very good at producing the single best-fit parameters, but not optimized for calculating 1σ error bars, since the program only provided the best-fit parameters without calculating the errors. However, the Markov chain is significantly long enough that at the end of the chain, the chi-square value and the parameters have mostly converged. In order to determine convergence manually, I looked at the last 7000 or so steps and noticed that the single best-fit values had not changed, and every change that moved to a higher chi-square moved back to the value that minimized the chi-square value. At this point, the parameters are essentially distributed normally with the mean at the best-fit value, so I can calculate the standard deviation of each parameter from its distribution of the last 1000 steps or so, which will give me the 1σ error bars I desire. I added this calculation to the end of the C process.

4.2 Python emcee approach

In addition to the single-variable MCMC process written in C, I also created an outside program in Python that utilized “emcee”, a self-contained MCMC program in Python (Foreman-Mackey, Hogg, and Lang 2013). Unlike the C version, “emcee” was created to exploit the usage of multiple processes. The beginning of the program spawns a set number of walkers, where the number has to be at least twice the length of the parameter space. This is done so that, in the limiting case that a walker only travels along one dimension in the parameter space, each dimension can be explored in either direction. For the initial conditions, “emcee” asks that the walkers start in a small Gaussian “ball” around the best guess for the parameters, which will then grow and expand quickly as the walkers begin to fully explore the N-dimensional parameter space.

For the MCMC process, the walker generates a random step that could be in any direction in the parameter space, not constrained in one dimension as the C version was. The Python program then calls the code in C to run the integrator and produce the chi-square value for that set of parameters. Using the Metropolis-Hastings conditions, it checks to see whether or not it accepts the step, and if it does it makes the step and adds one to the total number of acceptances. After the end of the preset number of runs, the program outputs the mean acceptance fraction, which is simply the number of acceptances divided by the number of steps taken in the process, with good acceptance fractions being somewhere between 0.25 and 0.5. If the acceptance fraction is higher, then the walkers are not exploring enough of the parameter space, and if it is lower, then the initial guess was not good and the walkers are exploring a low-density region in probability.

The main advantage this has over the C version is that the Python progresses can be multi-threaded, so that any number of walkers can be spawned off on different processors, streamlining the MCMC process and minimizing the length of time it takes. However, in order to make multiple processes work with the C program, I had to make the C code re-entrant, as the current version of the photodynamical model did not have the ability to have multiple instances of it running simultaneously. This amounted to making a new C structure of variables called “global data”, which is the set of variables that is used across functions in the integrator and re-created in every instance. The actual Kepler, RV, and astrometric datasets are still sent into arrays that are memory-allocated and initialized the first time the integrator is run, and simply remains in memory and accessed separately for each subsequent iteration of the integrator.

The output of the Python program contains the best fit estimates for the parameters, but due to the walkers exploring a large area in the parameter space, it also returns the

(marginalized) distribution of each parameter based on the acceptance fraction. Each marginalized parameter is distributed normally with the mean at or very near the best-guess initial value (since we know from the analysis in C11 that these values should give a very good fit), and the standard deviation from these distributions can be calculated in order to obtain 1σ error bars.

5. Analysis

5.1 C11 photometry only

In order to start analyzing the data, I decided to focus on the photometry only, since it had the highest amount of observations. I justified that the photometry would provide the highest contribution to the chi-square value, and thus would be the best dataset to begin attempting to maximize the fitting potential of the model. Indeed, opening results showed that the chi-squared value for just the photometry alone using the earliest model were still in the millions, so prioritizing the photometry was shown to be a good idea. However, I needed to make many adjustments to the parameter inputs in order for the model to run the analysis of KOI-126 properly.

5.1.1 *Coordinate system change*

At first, the model parameters described in C11 did not reproduce anything similar to the expected results (see Figure 12), so I started by applying a different set of parameters. After fitting the first transit event and running the MCMC process 10,000 times, I found a first group of values that described the first transit event well, with a reduced chi-square of 1.22. However, these values differed wildly from the numbers reported in C11. In particular, the mean anomaly

Figure 12: Side-by-side comparisons of the Kepler short-cadence data (left) and the original model setup, with (+Z) located towards the observer (right). This iteration of the model presented the 8 transits seen in the Kepler data as secondary eclipses, which when combined with the model assuming negligible flux from the low-mass binary, leaves a straight line of unobstructed flux from the star. In addition, the model introduced 6 spurious transit events located at half-periods between transits in the Kepler photometry, which would actually be secondary eclipses in the data.

of the orbit of the low-mass binary around the primary star was noticeably different, even after taking into account the two different epochs of observation, and the mutual inclination of the low-mass binary was lowered dramatically.

I then took this set of parameters and tried to fit the second transit event by itself. However, this also was a poor beginning fit and required many thousands of iterations on the MCMC process to create a second set of parameters that best described the second transit event, with a reduced chi-square value of 1.6. After repeating this process again with the third transit event, I had a reduced chi-square of 1.27 (see Table 1 for the initial parameters for each transit). Every set of parameters was largely different from the other sets, and this showed when, after

	Transit Event 1	Transit Event 2	Transit Event 3
Masses			
A (M_{\odot})	1.347	1.351	1.350
B (M_{\odot})	0.2413	0.2397	0.2396
C (M_{\odot})	0.2127	0.2099	0.2092
Radii			
A (R_{\odot})	2.0254	2.0932	2.4161
B (R_{\odot})	0.2200	0.2490	0.2963
C (R_{\odot})	0.2500	0.2389	0.2727
Orbital Parameters (A, (B, C))			
Time Epoch (BJD)	2455102.75	2455136.75	2455170.5
Period (Days)	33.9010	33.9010	33.9010
Semi-major Axis (AU)	0.2494	0.2494	0.2494
Eccentricity	0.3043	0.2999	0.3005
Argument of Periapse	52.78°	52.82°	53.79°
Mean Anomaly	241.24°	243.07°	241.73°
Inclination	91.950°	91.847°	91.385°
Longitude of Ascending Node	$\equiv 0.0^{\circ}$	359.93°	0.58°
Orbital Parameters (B, C)			
Time Epoch (BJD)	2455102.75	2455136.75	2455170.5
Period (Days)	0.99583	1.00761	1.01882
Semi-major Axis (AU)	0.015000	0.015118	0.015230
Eccentricity	0.02234	0.01145	0.69562
Argument of Periapse	359.99°	359.16°	302.39°
Mean Anomaly	359.69°	166.12°	359.08°
Inclination	65.000°	78.772°	114.272°
Longitude of Ascending Node	1.250°	19.67°	48.26°

Table 1: Physical and orbital parameters for each of the single transit events using the incorrect RH coordinate system, showing that the values of the orbital parameters for the low-mass binary stars change dramatically between transit events 2 and 3, more so than would be expected for even their strongly interacting orbits. This indicated that something was wrong with the current implementation of the model.

combining two or three transits together into single datasets, none of them had a reduced chi-square less than 3. In addition to calculating the best fit parameters, I also plotted the model overlaid on top of the Kepler photometry for the 1.5-day window around the center of the transit, as well as the positions of the two low-mass stars with respect to the heliocentric frame centered on the primary star (see Figures 12-14 for initial three transits). In particular, I plotted positions of the low-mass binary at 100 different places along the transit and superimposed 10 circles showing specific points ordered in time, each of them approximately 3 hours apart.

I then plotted the photometric model flux for the first transit using the parameters from C11 alongside the X-Y positions of the low-mass binary. The photodynamical model predicted no transit, showing a straight line through the Kepler photometry, but the positions showed that the low-mass binary was either passing in front of or behind the primary star. Indeed, the positions matched exactly with the same graphic showed in C11. Looking at the full 3D positions of each star, I noticed that during this supposed transit event, where the low-mass binary stars were supposed to be in front of the primary star, they were located in the (-Z) range. However, my code assumed a right-handed coordinate system and had (+Z) located towards the observer, in front of the primary star. By changing one comparison in the transit checking code from ($z > 0$) to ($z < 0$), I was able to recover a transit event happening at the epoch of the first transit using the parameters from C11, and the events were close to the Kepler photometry in both position and magnitude. Expanding this out to cover the first three transit events, I could tell that the physical and orbital parameters of C11 now were mostly consistent with the physical processes occurring in the KOI-126 system.

From these initially positive results, I stitched together two different datasets to run my model of photometry only. One was the original eight-transit dataset analyzed in C11, consisting

Figure 13: (Left) Model flux of the first transit using bad RH coordinate system, in green, overlaid on Kepler photometry, shown in blue. (Right) The X-Y positions of the low-mass stars during the first event in comparison with the primary star in the heliocentric frame, with the arrows pointing in the direction of time moving forward and the shades of the stars going from bluer to redder with time.

Figure 14: As in Figure 13, but with the second transit event. Here, the orbital parameters of the system have changed a good amount, but the overall structure of the system is similar to that of the first transit.

Figure 15: As in Figure 13, but with the third transit event. Here, the physical parameters of the system have wildly deviated from those of the first transit event, and the model fit to the photometry is poor from egress of the mutual transit through to the end.

originally of 17630 data points, while the second was all of the Kepler short-cadence photometry available, corresponding to 34 transits comprised of 74,200 data points, covering the range from 2009-2013. In order to run these large datasets in a reasonable amount of time, I used Harvard Research Computing’s Odyssey Cluster, which was able to perform these analyses overnight on multiple nodes of the cluster.

5.1.2. Fixing Jacobi Hierarchy

After running for long periods of time with both the 8 transit data and the 34 transit data, I noticed another interesting result occurring. I could not get the reduced chi-square value below 5 for the large datasets, and the difference between chi-square would stall out around 1000 runs to the large chi-square value. The original values from C11, used on the same set of data analyzed in the paper, led to a reduced chi-square of 11.32 – a terrible fit for the “best” parameters. This reduced chi-square had only managed to get down to 5.33 after 3000 runs, and

had not fluctuated much in the last 2000 runs of the MCMC process. For the full dataset, which at the time was being run using the Python version, the reduced chi-squares at beginning and end of the analysis were 18.67 and 5, respectively.

Looking at the parameters, I noticed that the program seemed to be sending the radius of star B (the slightly larger of the low-mass stars) to the radius of star C, and vice versa. The masses were still at the values in C11, so this did not seem to make much sense to me. I decided to probe it further and switch the masses as well, so that now star C was at the center of the Jacobi hierarchy, instead of star B as it had been originally. The results were immediately noticeable. The reduced chi-square value upon startup for the C11 data analysis, using the values from the paper, dropped by more than 75% to 2.62, twice as good as I had been getting after applying the MCMC process for thousands of steps before. There was an analogous drop in the chi-square value for the 34-transit dataset, confirming my belief that the system's Jacobi hierarchy had been previously entered into our photodynamical model incorrectly.

Looking back at why the code was not able to use the MCMC process to switch the values by itself, I realized I had set a much more strict constraint on the stellar masses compared to their radii by an order of magnitude. Thus, the photodynamical model was not finding any better solutions for the masses than the values I had given it, simply because it was not allowed to search outside of the potential minimum in which I had initialized it. However, since the radii were allowed to search more freely, they left the potential minimum I placed them in and found the better potential, but since the masses were not following the program stalled out. Had I allowed the masses to change as much as the radii, it is possible that the MCMC process could have switched the two stars completely, providing the correct Jacobi hierarchy for the KOI-126 system.

5.1.3. Limb-darkening and data cleaning

I was given a set of limb-darkening parameters that were considered standard for solar-type stars in the I-band (Claret 2000), and used those as fixed parameters in the model. However, C11 had a different set of values for the limb-darkening that he had used as free parameters. To standardize my analysis with theirs, I also made the two limb-darkening parameters free to vary in the parameter space, starting with the values reported in C11, which caused an immediate 10% drop in the chi-square value of the first run. However, after 1,000 runs, the chi-square value stabilized to a point only 600 chi-square below where runs with fixed limb-darkening parameters had reached, suggesting that having the correct values is important to start but is not very significant at the end of the fitting process.

With the chi-square value still a factor of 1.5 away from the value reported in C11, I decided to look at the actual datasets used in their analysis. In particular, I noticed that they had cleaned the data much more thoroughly than I had, which was most noticeable in the fourth transit dataset in Quarter 4, which was previously known to contain outliers for the photometry due to the strong linear trend outlined in Section 3. Removing the first 500 data points from the fourth transit reduced the chi-square by 10,000, or a factor of 33%, which brought the reduced chi-square down to 1.15. This suggested that I needed to re-clean the data, and to be more aggressive at removing outliers from the dataset, since most of these 500 data points were simple out-of-transit baseline observations.

In order to re-clean the data, I set up a function that calculates multiple limits to check the data values. If the photometric data point is ever 3σ greater than 1, with the error defined at that data point, I automatically remove it from the data set. Otherwise, the program looks at the 50 values around it in the data and calculates the standard deviation of these points, with the first

and last 25 data points being manually checked for outliers. If the mean of these 50 values is within 3σ of 1, then if the data point is also more than 3σ below 1, I remove it. If the mean of the nearest 50 values is much less than 1, then I know that the data points are in a transit, and I only calculate the standard deviation of the nearest 10 values. In this case, the mean is further away from each endpoint of the sequence, but the variance is larger. If the next data point is more than 3σ away from this mean, I remove it. This helps remove outliers in the center of transits which are more difficult to manually see and remove.

5.1.4. Light emission and final optimization

Finally, in order to maximize the similarities between my analysis and that from C11, I decided to model the low-mass binary as bodies that emit light, in contrast to how they had previously been modeled as pure occulters. This necessitated a slight change in how the photometric flux at each point inside a transit was calculated. Instead of star A having all of the flux, I instead set up two free parameters that were the ratios of the flux for star B to star A and star C to star A, and then reduced the amount of light coming from each star such that $F_A + F_B + F_C = 1$ outside of a transit. This only led to changes on the order of 10^{-4} originally, as the flux ratios between the primary star and each of the low-mass binary stars were at that order of magnitude, as reported by C11.

When in transit, the amount of light blocked from star A was reduced by that factor, but I also added in the flux from the two smaller stars. If the low-mass binary stars was also not mutually eclipsing at the time, then nothing else changed and the overall effect was simply to decrease the depth of the transit slightly. However, if there was a mutual eclipse between the two stars in the low-mass binary, then I determined which one was the closest to us and which was

between its companion and the primary star. Then, I blocked off a percentage of light equal to the overlap area between the two low-mass stars multiplied by the flux of the blocked star and divided by the area of the blocked star. This is in addition to the part of the code that already accounted for the overlap of the transits of the primary star by the low mass binary. This factor only changed the depth of the transit by a fraction of the 10^{-4} , and only produced a slight decrease in the reduced chi-square value.

All of the previous chi-square values were calculated with one run through the MCMC process, usually between 1,000 and 5,000 steps in the process, since this was about the feasible limit I could do in a reasonable time on my laptop. These were also calculated without making any estimates for the error bars. After finalizing the program with the above changes in the analysis, I realized that my optimization time was actually worse than previously calculated for single- or double-transit data sets. For the C11 dataset, since there were more inter-transit integrations that added time to the process, I ended up getting approximately 10 runs every 4 seconds. However, I noticed that the chi-square value was not changing much after 1,000 steps, so I decided to set up a 10,000 step MCMC process to run on Odyssey for the C11 dataset photometry. At the end of this long MCMC process, I also ran the photodynamical model for an additional 5,000 steps to calculate the spread of the distribution and obtain 1σ error bars for each parameter.

5.2 Full dataset photometry

Running the photodynamical model for the full dataset straight from the values in C11, however, produced bad results. The reduced chi-square value for the original run with their parameters was around 25. Performing MCMC analysis also did not improve the results very

much at first, and stopped any improvement after the first 1,000 steps. This suggested that my model was in a local minimum in the chi-square distribution, and that the walls of the well were too high for the MCMC process to escape it and continue to search for the global minimum in the density distribution.

Looking at the photometric output from the model after 1,000 steps in the MCMC process, I noticed that the values still produced good fits for the first 8 transits, although some of the shapes were slightly shifted due to alteration from MCMC. However, as time continued, and the photometric analysis explored the newer data from Kepler, the model values started to deviate from the data, and the deviations increased in strength with the latest transits. To combat this, I opened up the restrictions on the parameter space, which had been pretty strict due to the low error bars from C11, in order to explore more regions in the density distribution to find the global minimum.

The full dataset solution, as shown in Results, Section 7.1, was similar to the solution from C11, but enough of the parameters were outside the errors that the results from C11 are found to be inconsistent with the full set of Kepler photometry. My results give a reduced chi-square value of 1.15. The photometric model for this data set did match the observations well for the entire set of photometry, making this fit more likely for the observations than the values reported in C11. I then went back and repeated the analysis for the original data set used in C11, but started with the best set of parameters I found in my full dataset analysis. This lowered the reduced chi-square value to below 1.3 on the initial run, and the MCMC process did end up finding an even lower reduced chi-square value for the parameter set, which is also reported in Results Section 7.1.

5.3 Photometry + RV

For radial velocity, C11 used 10 data points from TRES that spanned about 5 months in 2010, along with 6 data points from the Tull Coudé Spectrograph at McDonald Observatory that cover almost a full year. Unlike transit observations, which must be taken when the system geometry is at a very specific point (the low-mass binary is between the observer and the primary star), RV observations can be performed at any point during the orbit of the star. Thus, I get a wider range of the orbit covered using RV data, which allows for tighter constraints on the orbital parameters of the low-mass binary with respect to the primary star, since we are measuring the movement of the primary star with this RV data.

In 2010, the TRES instrument was very new, and the velocity zero point and precision of the system had yet to be well constrained, so they were fluctuating heavily while the original observations of KOI-126 were taken. However, now that the instrument zero point and precision have settled down with technology upgrades, it is possible to re-reduce the observations with a better understanding of the data and receive more accurate results. To that end, I received cleaned versions of the first 10 data points from TRES, which differed slightly from the previous values but not significantly so. These values were given in km/s, but as the model uses AU/day, the values were converted before being read into the code. I used the six McDonald Observatory data points as they were, and ran the photodynamical model with just the 16 data points originally used by C11. However, something was off. The original runs were coming back with chi-square values greater than 1.7×10^7 , nearly all of it in the RV section. In addition, the velocities given by the program seemed to be, on average, smaller in magnitude than the values reported in C11, and the photometry was being shifted by approximately 30 minutes for each transit.

There were two main problems with the model here causing these issues, one with the analysis and one with the code itself. When I went back and closely re-read the RV section in C11, I noticed that they used a systematic offset for the motion of the barycenter of -27.278 km/s, which is why all of their data points fluctuated between -2 km/s and -44 km/s instead of being clustered around 0. By introducing this as a free parameter, I was able to eliminate the error causing the chi-square to reach into the millions. For the photometric shift, I realized that the exposure length was being read for each exposure, but saved over itself into a single variable each time, so the length of integration for the photodynamical model in each exposure was only set by the last exposure length in the file containing the observation times. If the last observation was an RV measurement, all of the data in the model was considered to have an exposure length of 30 minutes, the assumed exposure length for the RV data. I created an array of values and indexed into it for each exposure, which fixed the 30-minute shift issue in all of the Kepler photometry.

I ran the C version of the MCMC process with 10,000 steps for the 8-transit C11 dataset with its corresponding RVs, as well as the full 34-transit data set with all of the available RV data. This included 3 previously-unused data points from TRES around the same time that the others were taken in 2010, 4 more measurements taken in 2014, and an additional 6 observations from 2016, bringing the total number of RV observations up to 29. The results from these runs are shown in Results, Section 7.2, along with comparing them to the runs with the same photometry performed without RV data. The values in all of these runs are similar. The C11 analysis including the RV data actually shifted the radii value for the primary star and the larger star in the low-mass binary closer to the reported value, but it also pushed the radius of the smaller star in the low-mass binary further below its value in C11. Also of note is that the

eccentricity and inclination of the low-mass binary are slightly closer to their previously reported values in C11.

6. Astrometry

The newest addition to the photodynamical model, astrometric observations are particularly timely due to the observations of the Gaia satellite, as previously mentioned. However, since Gaia has yet to observe KOI-126, and earlier astrometry missions like Hipparcos did not observe this system, I will instead create and use simulated astrometric measurements to show the capabilities of the model. For the purposes of finding a best-fit model, I note that producing a model best-fit to a previous best-fit output of astrometric measurements from that model is suspicious, but this setup is mostly to confirm that the photodynamical model is handling the observations well for when Gaia data are available, and that the model still applies the system dynamics correctly to a new data exposure type, which had not previously been tested.

6.1 Synthetic astrometry

To create the simulated astrometry points from the photodynamical model, I must go through the same coordinate frame swaps as the radial velocity observations, switching from the heliocentric frame used in the photometry to the barycentric frame. Because there are so many photometric points, and because Gaia has a variable cadence, with around 6 observations in a week, and then no observations for a month, I decided to just use the Kepler long-cadence times for the synthetic astrometric data points.

For each observation time, I simply found the position of the primary star in the barycentric frame along both the X and Y axes. From this, I worked backwards to create astrometric observations as they would be seen with Gaia, without including the effect of parallax, which is dependent on the distance. If I were to include parallax, this would add another free parameter to the model, the distance to the system. However, in most cases accurate parallax measurements exist and the distance can be very accurately constrained, or it is completely unknown, and it can just be set to any value for simplicity. In the case of KOI-126, where no measurements have been taken but spectroscopy was available, I fit the spectroscopic parameters to the Dartmouth stellar evolution database isochrones and calculated a distance of 600 pc to the system.

Once all of the positions have been generated, I go back and replicate the Gaia cadence with the data. There are expected to be more astrometric data points than RV observations, as Gaia will go back to the system every few months and observe, whereas RVs do not necessarily return at any given point. However, there will still be orders of magnitude more photometric observations since it is a Kepler object. Thus, the values from the fit are still most tightly constrained by the Kepler photometry, although the RV and the astrometry do provide good measurements on the masses of the three bodies.

6.2 Astrometric errors

In order to simulate the observations of real data, I will also create simulated uncertainties in the measurement of the astrometric movement of the primary star. For the magnitude of the uncertainties, I again refer to Perryman et al. (2014), which states that the overall uncertainty is made up of the errors in centroid accuracy for each CCD on Gaia and the systematic errors from

calibration and instrument modeling. For a 13th magnitude star such as KOI-126, the uncertainty in the astrometric position of the star in Gaia's field of view is 41.6 microarcseconds, whereas the uncertainty in the parallax is 12.9 microarcseconds. Since the estimated astrometric signature has a magnitude around 100 microarcseconds at a distance of 600 pc, it will be observable by Gaia.

For each data point, I added in the uncertainty as noise to the measurement, which is normally distributed around 0 with the reported error as the standard deviation. At 600 pc, this caused most of the signal to smear out, and there was not much of the original torus of astrometry able to be seen. Thus, I decided to also shift in the system to a distance of 100 pc, 1 order of magnitude closer. Keeping KOI-126 at the same brightness, since its apparent magnitude is known, I pick up an order of magnitude in the strength of the signal while the astrometric errors remain the same, so the strength of the astrometric signal is approximately 600 microarcseconds. 100 pc is a good general distance estimate for systems that will be discovered by TESS.

6.3 Refitting using astrometry

After creating the simulated astrometry, I ran the C single-variable MCMC process on the dataset from C11 for only 1,000 steps, with the initial parameters near their best fit values from the earlier analysis, for the system at both 600 pc and 100 pc (see Figure 19). Even though the signal is more smeared out for the 600 pc system, the differences between the model and the data are still comparable since the noise is randomly distributed with the same standard deviation in both models. Since the simulated astrometry came from a similar setup in the parameter space, the overall chi-square for the model increases by approximately 40%, but with 118 more data

Figure 16: (Left) Simulated Gaia astrometry, with the pure model (green) and the model plus noise (blue) for system at a distance of 600 pc. (Right) Same as left, but with the system instead at 100 pc, so the signal is an order of magnitude stronger than the noise.

points from the astrometry. This corresponds to a reduced chi-square for both systems of about 1.65, showing that the model is able to handle the new astrometric data read-in and output correctly.

As stated previously, this is not an attempt to better constrain the parameters of the system using the simulated astrometry, because I am using the same model to produce the data and to attempt to fit the data. However, for testing purposes, it fulfills its duty and allows me to see what the results would be if Gaia astrometry existed for this system, which hopefully could happen soon. The refitted model has a noticeable increase in the reduced chi-square value, and there does not seem to be any significant difference in the best-fit parameters when fitted with the astrometry as compared to without the astrometry. In any case, for stellar and planetary systems detected by Gaia (and TESS) in the near future, the model will be able to accurately portray the Gaia data and make inferences on the dynamical properties of such interesting systems.

7. Results

7.1 Photometry only

	C11	8 Transits (Original Run)	34 Transits
Masses			
A (M_{\odot})	1.347 ± 0.032	$1.347^{+0.005}_{-0.006}$	$1.347^{+0.0007}_{-0.0007}$
B (M_{\odot})	0.2413 ± 0.0030	$0.2413^{+0.008}_{-0.006}$	$0.2413^{+0.0006}_{-0.0007}$
C (M_{\odot})	0.2127 ± 0.0026	$0.2127^{+0.005}_{-0.006}$	$0.2127^{+0.0005}_{-0.0007}$
Radii			
A (R_{\odot})	2.0254 ± 0.0098	$2.0190^{+0.005}_{-0.006}$	$2.0201^{+0.0007}_{-0.0007}$
B (R_{\odot})	0.2543 ± 0.0014	$0.2537^{+0.009}_{-0.003}$	$0.2534^{+0.0006}_{-0.0006}$
C (R_{\odot})	0.2318 ± 0.0013	$0.2312^{+0.006}_{-0.004}$	$0.2307^{+0.0007}_{-0.0008}$
Orbital Parameters (A, (B, C))			
Time Epoch (BJD)	2455170.5	2455170.5	2455170.5
Period (Days)	33.9214 ± 0.0013	$33.9214^{+0.001}_{-0.002}$	$33.9214^{+0.0008}_{-0.0002}$
Semi-major Axis (AU)	0.2495 ± 0.0017	$0.2495^{+0.001}_{-0.002}$	$0.2495^{+0.0010}_{-0.0003}$
Eccentricity	0.3043 ± 0.0024	$0.3047^{+0.005}_{-0.007}$	$0.3053^{+0.0007}_{-0.0010}$
Argument of Periapse	$52.88^{\circ} \pm 0.33^{\circ}$	$52.88^{+0.67}_{-0.77}$	$52.46^{+0.40}_{-0.50}$
Mean Anomaly	$19.87^{\circ} \pm 0.29^{\circ}$	$19.87^{+0.59}_{-0.35}$	$20.09^{+0.45}_{-0.27}$
Inclination	$92.100^{\circ} \pm 0.016^{\circ}$	$92.100^{+0.374}_{-0.467}$	$92.110^{+0.198}_{-0.312}$
Longitude of Ascending Node	$\equiv 0^{\circ}$	$\equiv 0^{\circ}$	$\equiv 0^{\circ}$
Orbital Parameters (B, C)			
Time Epoch (BJD)	2455170.5	2455170.5	2455170.5
Period (Days)	1.76713 ± 0.00019	$1.76713^{+0.00017}_{-0.00013}$	$1.76713^{+0.00015}_{-0.00009}$
Semi-major Axis (AU)	0.021986 ± 0.000090	$0.021986^{+0.00008}_{-0.00006}$	$0.021986^{+0.00007}_{-0.00004}$
Eccentricity	0.02234 ± 0.00036	$0.02144^{+0.0029}_{-0.0065}$	$0.02096^{+0.00060}_{-0.00090}$
Argument of Periapse	$89.52^{\circ} \pm 0.42^{\circ}$	$89.19^{+0.73}_{-0.58}$	$88.79^{+0.59}_{-0.52}$
Mean Anomaly	$355.66^{\circ} \pm 0.42^{\circ}$	$356.27^{+0.55}_{-0.64}$	$356.40^{+0.28}_{-0.53}$
Inclination	$96.907^{\circ} \pm 0.044^{\circ}$	$97.114^{+0.744}_{-0.666}$	$96.967^{+0.684}_{-0.601}$
Longitude of Ascending Node	$8.012^{\circ} \pm 0.039^{\circ}$	$8.048^{+0.316}_{-0.361}$	$8.010^{+0.245}_{-0.330}$
Stellar Flux and RV Parameters			
u_1	0.39 ± 0.03	$0.32^{+0.02}_{-0.06}$	$0.32^{+0.008}_{-0.006}$
u_2	0.22 ± 0.04	$0.27^{+0.08}_{-0.06}$	$0.26^{+0.011}_{-0.008}$
γ_{sys} (km/s)	-27.278 ± 0.024	N/A	N/A
γ_{TVM} (km/s)	-0.26 ± 0.17	N/A	N/A
F_B/F_A	$(3.26 \pm 0.24) \times 10^{-4}$	$(3.26^{+0.08}_{-0.06}) \times 10^{-4}$	$(3.33^{+0.07}_{-0.05}) \times 10^{-4}$
F_C/F_A	$(2.24 \pm 0.48) \times 10^{-4}$	$(2.24 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-4}$	$(2.34^{+0.05}_{-0.07}) \times 10^{-4}$

Table 2: The best-fit values and 1σ error bars for C11, my best fit for the first 8 transits analyzed in C11, and for the entire photometric dataset of 34 transits. C11 provided good analysis for the first 8 transits, but these values actually provide a poor fit for all 34 transits, requiring a new fit.

Figure 17: (Left) Model flux for the first two transit events using the LH coordinate system and the C single-parameter approach overlaid on top of the Kepler photometry. (Right) The X-Y positions of the low-mass stars during each event, with the arrows pointing in the direction of time moving forward and the shades of the stars going from bluer to redder with time. These fits are much better than the early versions, allowing for mutual eclipses and consistent evolution of the orbital parameters.

Figure 18: Same as Figure 17, but with transit events 3-5. Slight mutual eclipse occurs in transit 5, near the sharp egress changes as one low-mass star exits transit.

Figure 19: As in Figure 17, but with transit events 6-8. Slight mutual eclipse occurs in transit 6, near the sharp egress changes as one low-mass star exits transit.

7.2 Photometry + RV

	New 8 Transits + RV	34 Transits + RV
Masses		
A (M_{\odot})	1.347 ± 0.005	1.347 ± 0.0004
B (M_{\odot})	$0.2413^{+0.006}_{-0.005}$	$0.2413^{+0.0003}_{-0.0004}$
C (M_{\odot})	0.2127 ± 0.005	0.2127 ± 0.0004
Radii		
A (R_{\odot})	$2.0153^{+0.005}_{-0.004}$	$2.0241^{+0.0003}_{-0.0005}$
B (R_{\odot})	0.2531 ± 0.009	0.2534 ± 0.0004
C (R_{\odot})	$0.2318^{+0.004}_{-0.006}$	$0.2313^{+0.0005}_{-0.0004}$
Orbital Parameters (A, (B, C))		
Time Epoch (BJD)	2455170.5	2455170.5
Period (Days)	$33.9214^{+0.0005}_{-0.0002}$	$33.9214^{+0.00014}_{-0.00018}$
Semi-major Axis (AU)	$0.2495^{+0.0005}_{-0.0002}$	$0.2495^{+0.00014}_{-0.00018}$
Eccentricity	$0.3051^{+0.0012}_{-0.0009}$	$0.3053^{+0.00039}_{-0.00028}$
Argument of Periapse	$52.46^{\circ+0.46}_{-0.68}$	$52.46^{\circ} \pm 0.35$
Mean Anomaly	$20.09^{\circ+0.34}_{-0.35}$	$20.09^{\circ+0.22}_{-0.19}$
Inclination	$92.110^{\circ+0.418}_{-0.370}$	$92.110^{\circ+0.279}_{-0.308}$
Longitude of Ascending Node	$\equiv 0^{\circ}$	$\equiv 0^{\circ}$
Orbital Parameters (B, C)		
Time Epoch (BJD)	2455170.5	2455170.5
Period (Days)	$1.76713^{+0.00090}_{-0.00028}$	$1.76713^{+0.000121}_{-0.000069}$
Semi-major Axis (AU)	$0.021986^{+0.00040}_{-0.00013}$	$0.021986^{+0.000058}_{-0.000033}$
Eccentricity	$0.02104^{+0.00035}_{-0.00048}$	$0.02096^{+0.00019}_{-0.00024}$
Argument of Periapse	$88.79^{\circ+0.45}_{-0.49}$	$88.79^{\circ+0.33}_{-0.38}$
Mean Anomaly	$356.40^{\circ+0.39}_{-0.60}$	$356.40^{\circ+0.32}_{-0.43}$
Inclination	$96.967^{\circ+0.731}_{-0.465}$	$96.967^{\circ+0.075}_{-0.113}$
Longitude of Ascending Node	$7.940^{\circ+0.499}_{-0.559}$	$8.010^{\circ+0.331}_{-0.285}$
Stellar Flux and RV Parameters		
u_1	$0.31^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	$0.33^{+0.005}_{-0.003}$
u_2	$0.24^{+0.02}_{-0.01}$	$0.30^{+0.005}_{-0.004}$
γ_{sys} (km/s)	$-28.240^{+0.123}_{-0.068}$	$-27.766^{+0.039}_{-0.023}$
γ_{TvM} (km/s)	-0.32 ± 0.06	$0.60^{+0.04}_{-0.02}$
F_B/F_A	$(3.17^{+0.03}_{-0.04}) \times 10^{-4}$	$(3.33 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-4}$
F_C/F_A	$(2.62 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-4}$	$(1.90 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-4}$

Table 3: Results when run for the C11 and full datasets, with the available RV observations for that dataset. There were 16 total RV measurements in the C11 analysis and 29 in the full dataset.

Figure 20: (Top) RV model data (green) plotted over model function (blue). (Bottom) RV residuals. The model and residuals are similar to those plotted in Figure 6.

7.3 Error Analysis

For the error analysis, I originally tried to use the C single-variable MCMC approach and calculate the deviations of each accepted jump in the parameter space. However, when the model was well settled, only 0.1% of all steps were being accepted, and this proved to be a non-practical approach. I then attempted to measure the variance of each movement made by the MCMC process, regardless of whether or not it was accepted. This provided a much better histogram, but since the program only changed one parameter at a time, this vastly oversampled the initial best-fit values. Even dividing this maximum value by the number of parameters, so that in principle it would take out every sample that was not a jump by this parameter, the histogram was still too large at this value, and the program was not calculating tenable 1σ error bars.

Therefore, I decided to work within the Python “emcee” framework, as that automatically produced quantiles for each parameter as part of the analysis. I took the best-fit parameters after the C single-variable approach had settled down and ran them through “emcee” for 5000 steps, saving the 1σ quantiles on either side of the mean as the upper and lower error bars. I also ran the results through Dan Foreman-Mackey’s “corner.py” routine, which provides an easy to use way to marginalize over each parameter in the distribution and show the 1-D and 2-D histograms for each parameter and set of parameters (see Figure 20 for an example). I performed this for each of the main sets of data, which is comprised of C11 or full photometry, with or without RVs and astrometry, and the results were very similar.

Figure 21: A subset of the triangle covariance plot created by Dan Foreman-Mackey’s “corner.py” routine that marginalizes over each dimension and plots 1-D and 2-D histograms for each parameter. The truth values, shown here as blue lines, are the best-fit parameters as determined by the C single-variable MCMC approach, whereas the histogram and distributions come from the Python “emcee” approach.

8. Discussion

8.1 C11 Analysis

The first goal of this paper is to reproduce the analysis performed on KOI-126 by Josh Carter and his colleagues from their 2011 paper, where they obtained 5 quarters of long-cadence Kepler photometry, 3 quarters of short-cadence Kepler photometry, and 16 radial velocity data points from TRES in Arizona and the Tull Coudé Spectrograph at McDonald Observatory in Texas. I also gathered the same data, and decided to test the analysis for the photometry only, since the Kepler photometry dominated the total amount of data, with 17,425 short-cadence data points.

There were some differences in our analysis methods. For the Kepler photometry, C11 assumed that the orbiting bodies contributed flux to the system, whereas my code originally did not, although that feature was also added to test its impact on the model fit. For KOI-126, their assumption is more accurate, considering the orbiting bodies in this system are low-mass red dwarf stars, not planets, and they discovered mutual eclipses of the low-mass binary stars as they simultaneously passed in front of the primary star. However, our original assumption was not without merit, because C11 measured the flux of these bodies to be around 3×10^{-4} of the flux from the primary star, which is low enough that the amount of light blocked from the primary star is significantly more than the amount of light produced by the low-mass star. Each low-mass star is approximately one-quarter the size of the Sun, and the primary star's radius is approximately 2 solar radii. Thus, the ratio of their areas is about 1/64, or 1.56%, and the amount of light blocked by the low-mass star is more than 50 times the amount of light that each low-mass star produces, which is low enough that I consider the low-mass stars as bodies that do not emit light for the purposes of the photometric analysis. I ran the analysis with both assumptions,

and the overall chi-square difference was only around 100, so it did not have much of an effect on the best-fit model.

Another difference was in the method used for fitting. C11 used a Levenberg-Marquardt (L-M) algorithm to minimize the chi-square value of their fit, whereas I used an MCMC process. The L-M algorithm is also an iterative procedure, similar to MCMC, but each step in the process is instead defined by a linearization of the fitting function, so that the function at the new estimate is approximately equal to the function at the old estimate plus the gradient of the function with respect to the initial guess (Levenberg 1944, Marquardt 1963). This drives down the delta between estimates to smaller and smaller values, until the chi-square difference between the data and the model is small. However, like many other fitting algorithms, L-M may only find a local non-global minimum closest to the initial guess and get stuck in the potential well, not able to escape and find the global minimum. As seen in Figure 21, my implementation of MCMC sampling showed no large covariances between parameters and multiple local minima sampled by the program.

One more possible reason for different results is due to the different integration lengths used when integrating outside of transit. The maximum step size in C11's implementation of a Bulirsch-Stoer algorithm was 3 min, or approximately 0.1% of the period of the low-mass binary around the primary star. Between each of the 1.5 day transit windows is a non-transit baseline longer than 32 days. So C11 performed over 15,000 integrations between successive transits in the observation. However, in order to save time on the full dataset modeling with more than 4 times as much data, I increased the length of time per integration outside of exposures to the jump between two consecutive exposures. This does not affect the model during the transit, but

the large jump in exposure times between transits could be causing a slight change in the output of the photodynamical model.

8.2 Full Dataset

The second goal of this paper is to expand the scope of the analysis and use the full Kepler dataset for KOI-126. Nobody has since revisited this system with a photodynamical model since C11, although there are 12 more quarters of Kepler data available on MAST up to 2013, when the original Kepler mission was suspended due to the failure of the second reaction wheel. In addition, there have also been 13 more observations by TRES, 3 in 2010 around the other observations, 4 in 2014m and 6 in 2016. Thus, the full baseline of these observations spans from late 2009 for the original Kepler data and the McDonald radial velocity observations, out to 2013 for Kepler and 2016 for TRES. In total, there were 73637 data points combined from Kepler short-cadence photometry and RV measurements. The analysis of the photometry alone necessitated the use of a dedicated computer for the C version of the MCMC process, as knowing the result to the previous step is required to analyze the next step, so it cannot handle multiple threads. The single process MCMC approach took 15 hours to run the entire photometric dataset for 10,000 steps. Adding in the radial velocity added a small but significant amount of time to the analysis, even though there are only 29 RV data points from TRES and McDonald, because of the long time baseline that is created by integrating out to the 2016 TRES data points.

For this system, I also used a Python variant of the “emcee” program with an implementation of a multiple-step Metropolis-Hastings algorithm, without the production of error bars for optimization of available computer time. This runs faster than the normal selection

using “emcee” that includes error bars, but slower per run than the C version which runs more overall runs because it takes one Metropolis-Hastings step at a time. This was being run simultaneously with the C version on the shorter dataset on two separate computers. The results shown were drawn from a run consisting of 42 walkers each taking 500 steps, for a total of 21,000 steps in the MCMC process to calculate 1σ error bars. This produced a reduced chi-square value of 1.09, better than the value for the 8-transit dataset but still worse than reported in C11.

8.3 Evolution of System

The low-mass stars are in such a close orbit around each other (less than 5 solar radii separate them), and they orbit the main solar-type star at only $2/3$ the distance that Mercury orbits the Sun. Therefore, the orbital mechanics in this system are somewhat chaotic, and the orbits are constantly evolving from transit to transit. The orbital parameters need to be specified at a certain epoch corresponding to one of the transits, as they change significantly enough between transits that the photodynamical model would take a long time to converge to the correct set of parameters, if it converges at all, if the initial values from C11 were used at a different epoch.

Therefore, this evolution of the mechanics in the system also provides strong constraints on the parameters. Indeed, just adding more transits, and continuing to model the evolution of the system through almost 4 years of observations, I was able to determine that some of the values reported in C11 were just slightly off. However, this difference was significant enough that small-scale model deviations from the data started occurring in transit 11, about 100 days after the end of the C11 dataset, and by the end of the 34 transits the entire model was off, predicting

Parameter	Transit 1	Transit 12	Transit 23	Transit 34
Orbital Parameters (A, (B, C))				
Argument of Periapse	51.429	57.506	65.667	72.938
Mean Anomaly	19.112	17.501	12.426	8.629
Inclination	92.286	92.081	92.600	91.985
Longitude of Ascending Node	359.93	0.761	0.006	0.660
Orbital Parameters (B, C)				
Argument of Periapse	4.344	199.28	246.35	271.36
Mean Anomaly	186.80	182.59	12.923	20.667
Inclination	93.575	97.555	87.544	99.381
Longitude of Ascending Node	9.320	353.19	7.834	355.19

Table 4: The evolution of the 4 orbital angles in the system throughout the 4 years of Kepler photometric observations.

Figure 22: (Left) Evolution of low-mass binary eccentricity over 4 years, showing oscillations around 0.01 with spikes to 0.03. (Right) Evolution of the low-mass binary inclination over 4 years, showing a nice periodic variation from between 85 and 100 degrees, which allows for mutual eclipses of one star in the low-mass binary by the other.

Figure 23: (Left): Evolution of the argument of periastron of the low-mass binary over 4 years, which is constantly cycling from 0 to 360 degrees. (Right): Evolution of the longitude of the ascending node of the low-mass binary over 4 years. The longitude of the ascending node of the primary star is unconstrained and set to 0 at BJD = 2455170.5, and then allowed to move freely, and is the frame that the graphed longitude is measured with respect to.

values that were wildly inconsistent with the Kepler photometry. With the new set of parameters only slightly different than the old, this shows that the evolution of the system does provide tight constraints on the parameters. In addition, these evolutionary tracks can be modeled and propagated forward to the present day to determine the current system parameters, if the system is viewed by TESS or other telescopes.

8.4 Photometry alone vs. Photometry + RV

For strongly interacting systems like KOI-126, transit timing and duration variations in the Kepler photometry would be able to determine constraints on the masses of the objects in the system. However, the classical approach to measure the masses of an orbiting body is to measure the radial velocity perturbations of the primary star in the system, and this provides a lower limit

on the mass of the perturbing body, as well as the orbital period and semi-major axis, which can also be determined with transits.

I ran the analysis on the system both with and without RV for both sets of photometric data, to see how much of an effect it would have on the overall parameter fitting. Interestingly enough, both RV datasets provided large reduced chi-square values and changed a few parameters in the system, most notably the orbital angles, as those are allowed to vary the most in my analysis. The reduced chi-square of the 16 original RV data points in my analysis was around 5, which caused an increase in the overall reduced chi-square value from 1.13 to 1.15. This effect was even more pronounced for the full photometric dataset with the 29 RV observations, as these measurements had a reduced chi-square of 7, although the overall reduced chi-square remained at 1.09 due to the overwhelming significance of the Kepler photometry, with more than 2500 times as many data points.

8.5 Astrometry

The third goal of this paper is to increase the amount of data that can be used in a photodynamical model by including astrometric measurements. With the advent of Gaia data in the near future, the first batch already having been released, adding the ability to measure astrometry to photodynamical models will improve the constraints that the model can put on the data by increasing the number of options available. For example, if there are no RV observations for a system but transit photometry and astrometry both exist, the astrometric data points can still complement the radius measurements from the photometry by providing restrictions on the mass and orbital parameters of the systems, similar to what RV can do. Alternatively, if the system is not eclipsing but has RV and astrometry observations, at least the mass and some of the orbital

parameters can be constrained, which provides some knowledge of the physical parameters for the system, and probabilistic ranges can also be given for unconstrained parameters, such as the radius of the orbiting body.

9. Conclusion

In this paper I analyzed the triply-eclipsing hierarchical stellar system KOI-126, comprised of a solar-type primary star and two low-mass stars (approximately $\frac{1}{4}$ of a solar mass each) in a binary orbit which was first investigated by Carter et al. in 2011, abbreviated to C11. I performed a similar analysis to C11 on 8 transits of the system over 3 quarters of short-cadence Kepler data and 18 radial velocity data points from TRES and McDonald observatory, and originally produced similar results at the 1σ level for most of the parameters. My analysis procedures differed from C11 for integration step times, best-fit model algorithm, and initially flux from the low mass binary stars, but the values produced in this stage of the analysis were not too different as to suggest a new model was necessary.

However, I also extended the amount of data used in the analysis to the full set of 34 transits comprising 13 quarters of short-cadence Kepler photometry up to 2013 and 13 additional data points from TRES in 2010, 2014, and 2016. This analysis actually showed that the parameters in C11 are not consistent with the overall trajectory of the system. They are a good fit for the first 8 transits, but over the next three years the model deviates increasingly strongly from the data, and is noticeably inaccurate at the end of the full dataset. After releasing the parameter constraints slightly to allow the values to vary more, I found a solution that fit all 34 transits well, and re-analyzed the original 8 transits with these parameters to test the accuracy of the new model.

The system's tight binary of low-mass stars is in a <2 day orbit, and the center of mass of the binary orbits the third star at ~34 days, so the system is slightly chaotic and the orbital parameters are subtly yet constantly changing throughout time. This gives the model tight constraints on the overall structure of the system, as slight variations in the orbits can cause the evolution to behave much differently. KOI-126 provides an excellent view into how strange systems like this one have evolved over time. In addition, further observations of KOI-126 would be able to tell us whether the model developed here can provide predictive power on the parameters of the system. In particular, observations from TESS and continued RV follow-up from ground-based spectrographs would be precise enough to be able to see if the current version of the model holds. Conversely, if the model no longer holds, these new observations can further refine the best-fit model, just as I was able to do by adding in the full Kepler photometric data set and an additional set of RV observations.

Also, additional work could be done to measure the apsidal constant k_2 , which tells how much tidal distortion has affected the apsidal motion of the low-mass binary stars. Specifically, stars with such low masses as KOI-126 B & C have yet to receive reliable constraints on k_2 , although if each star is modeled as a polytrope with index $n = 1.5$, the expected value would be around 0.15 (Brooker and Olle 1955). If the full Kepler photometry can provide measurements of k_2 , future work to obtain these would be well received. This measurement, however, is beyond the scope of the current abilities for this photodynamical model.

Adding astrometry to this photodynamical model provided a third set of constraints on systems, and the ability to be more flexible with the amount and types of data required to run the photodynamical model. Astrometry will be specifically helpful in constraining orbital parameters, especially the longitude of ascending node of the outer orbit of KOI-126. Transits

and RVs cannot determine the longitude of ascending node, as transits do not provide any information on the angle at which the companion is passing across its star in the two-dimensional plane of the sky, only the impact parameter of the orbit. RVs only provide the z-dimension of the orbit, and the longitude of ascending node is the angle defined in the x-y direction. Also, astrometry can provide alternative data points for when RV is unavailable, which can occur with fainter stars that are visible with Gaia but not visible from the ground, for extremely active stars, or for stars that rotate very rapidly. With Gaia releasing more astrometric measurements in the near future, many systems will be able to benefit from this third observational type. In addition, the upcoming launch of TESS will provide many eclipsing systems that are bright targets, which will be viewed by Gaia and by ground-based spectrographs to create the next generation of data for these photodynamical models.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Dr. Matthew Holman and Dr. Matthew Payne for advising my senior research thesis, Dr. Sam Quinn and Dr. George Zhou for agreeing to serve as external readers, and Prof. David Charbonneau for overseeing the weekly thesis progress presentations as a part of the Astronomy 99 class, as well as all of my classmates at Harvard University for their input on my progress. I am particularly grateful to Prof. David Latham, Dr. Allyson Bieryla, Dr. Sam Quinn, and the rest of the TRES team for detailing the data analysis procedure and providing new radial velocity datasets from TRES, as well as more accurate data points for the older observations already in use. I am also thankful for the assistance of my family, my friends, and my roommates, who have supported me throughout the entire project. This project made use of the SIMBAD database, operated at CDS, Strasbourg, France. Some of the data presented in this paper were obtained from the Barbara A. Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes (MAST), organized by the Space Telescope Science Institute (STScI). STScI is operated by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under NASA contract NAS5-26555. Support for MAST for non-HST data is provided by the NASA Office of Space Science via grant NNX09AF08G and by other grants and contracts. This paper includes data collected by the Kepler mission. Funding for the Kepler mission is provided by the NASA Science Mission directorate. Some of the computations in this paper were run on the Odyssey computer cluster, which is supported by the FAS Division of Science, Research Computing Group, at Harvard University.

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